

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Glucose is a simple sugar with six carbon atoms and is the human body's key source of energy, through aerobic respiration, providing about 3.75 kilocalories (16 kilojoules) of food energy per gram (Wong, 2011). Glucose is sometimes referred to as blood sugar and a common medical analyte measured in blood samples. Breakdown of carbohydrates (e.g. starch) yields mono- and disaccharides, most of which is glucose. Through glycolysis and later in the reactions of the citric acid cycle and oxidative phosphorylation, glucose is oxidized to eventually form CO₂ and water, yielding energy mostly in the form of ATP (Adenosine Triphosphate) (Nelson and Cox, 2017).

The blood sugar concentration or blood glucose level is the amount of glucose (sugar) present in the blood of a human or animal (Rhoads and Rhoads, 2013). The body naturally tightly regulates blood glucose levels as a part of metabolic homeostasis. The insulin reaction and other mechanisms, regulate the concentration of glucose in the blood (Alberts *et al.*, 2015). Glucose levels are usually lowest in the morning, before the first meal of the day (termed 'the fasting level'), and rise after meals for an hour or two by a few millimolar. Blood sugar levels outside the normal range may be an indicator of a medical condition (American Diabetes Association, 2019). A persistently high level is referred to as hyperglycemia; low levels are referred to as hypoglycemia (National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases. (2016). The international standard way of measuring blood glucose levels is in terms of a molar concentration, measured in mmol/L (millimoles per liter) or in mg/dL (milligrams per deciliter). Since the molecular weight of glucose

$C_6H_{12}O_6$ is 180, for the measurement of glucose, the difference between the two scales is a factor of 18, so that 1 mmol/L of glucose is equivalent to 18 mg/dL (World Health Organization, 2006).

Glycemic index (GI) is the ranking of foods based on postprandial glucose response compared with a reference food. High glycemic index foods produce high concentrations of blood glucose and increase insulin demand and could plausibly contribute to the development of type 2 diabetes (Ludwig, 2002). GI is usually applied in the context of the quantity of the food and the amount of carbohydrate in the food that is actually consumed. A related measure, the glycemic load (GL), factors this by multiplying the GI of the food in question by the carbohydrate content of the actual consumed serving (Salmerón *et al.*, 1997). Low GI diets are essential to address blood glucose control as consumption of foods with a high GI is hypothesized to contribute to insulin resistance, which is associated with an increased risk of diabetes mellitus, obesity, cardiovascular disease, and some cancers (Brand-Miller *et al.*, 2002). The upsurge in the incidence and prevalence of metabolic diseases (such as diabetes mellitus) worldwide and in Nigeria in particular is a challenge for urgent action in the adoption of appropriate dietary management in patients with metabolic diseases and also in the prevention of these diseases in healthy individuals. This is particular of importance in Nigeria where carbohydrate staple food sources form the bulk of diet available to the majority of the population (Ogbera *et al.*, 2010).

Understanding the impact of commonly consumed foods in North Central Nigeria is crucial for addressing public health concerns, particularly those related to blood glucose levels. Analyzing the glycemic impact of these foods provides valuable insights into how dietary habits influence the prevalence of diabetes and other metabolic disorders in the region.

Foods that cause rapid spikes in blood glucose can contribute to the development of insulin resistance, obesity, and type 2 diabetes, all of which are significant public health challenges (Adebamowo *et al.*, 2009).

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

In North Central Nigeria, dietary patterns are predominantly based on carbohydrate-rich staples such as yam, cassava, maize, and rice. The impact of these commonly consumed foods on blood glucose levels remains inadequately studied, posing a significant gap in understanding the region's public health challenges. With the increasing prevalence of diabetes mellitus and other metabolic disorders in Nigeria, there is an urgent need to analyze the glycemic impact of these dietary staples. Elevated blood glucose levels contribute to the development of insulin resistance, obesity, and type 2 diabetes, conditions that are becoming alarmingly common in the region.

The absence of region-specific data in current dietary guidelines and interventions hampers their ability to effectively prevent and manage metabolic diseases. Lacking precise information on the impact of local foods on blood glucose levels leaves healthcare providers and policymakers ill-equipped to develop suitable dietary recommendations. This research aims to fill this critical gap by providing detailed analysis and insights into the blood glucose response elicited by commonly consumed foods in North Central Nigeria. Such data is essential for developing targeted nutritional guidelines that can mitigate the rising tide of diabetes and enhance the overall health outcomes of the population in this region.

1.3 Justification of the study

The increasing prevalence of diabetes mellitus and other metabolic disorders in North Central Nigeria is a significant public health concern. This region, characterized by a diet heavily reliant on carbohydrate-rich staples such as yam, cassava, maize, and rice, faces unique nutritional challenges that are inadequately addressed by current dietary guidelines. Understanding the glycemic impact of these commonly consumed foods is essential for several reasons.

Firstly, analyzing the blood glucose response to these foods will provide valuable data that can inform region-specific dietary recommendations. Existing guidelines often rely on generalized data that may not accurately reflect the dietary habits and metabolic responses of the North Central Nigerian population. By tailoring recommendations based on local food consumption patterns, healthcare providers can more effectively manage and prevent metabolic diseases.

Secondly, the insights gained from this study will aid in the development of targeted interventions aimed at reducing the incidence of diabetes, obesity, and related conditions. High glycemic index foods contribute to rapid spikes in blood glucose levels, leading to insulin resistance and other metabolic disorders. Identifying foods that cause significant glycemic responses can help in designing public health strategies that promote healthier eating habits.

1.4 Aim and Objectives of The Study

The aim of this study is to analyze the blood glucose response to some commonly consumed foods in North Central, Nigeria.

The specific objectives include:

- i. To identify the commonly consumed foods and their respective ingredients in North central, Nigeria through the administration of questionnaire.
- ii. To evaluate the blood glucose level of some selected locally consumed foods in North Central Nigeria.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Food and Nutrition

Food and nutrition are fundamental components of human health, providing the necessary nutrients to maintain bodily functions, promote growth, and support overall well-being (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018; Gropper and Smith, 2016). Nutrition science explores how the body uses food to sustain life and prevent diseases, emphasizing the importance of a balanced diet rich in various nutrients (Sizer and Whitney, 2017).

Macronutrients are essential nutrients required in large quantities, including carbohydrates, proteins, and fats. Carbohydrates are the primary energy source for the body, essential for brain function and physical activity. Foods such as grains, fruits, and vegetables are rich in carbohydrates, providing glucose, which is vital for cellular energy (Gropper and Smith, 2016). Proteins, composed of amino acids, are crucial for building and repairing tissues, producing enzymes and hormones, and supporting immune function. High-quality protein sources include meat, fish, dairy products, eggs, and plant-based options like beans and lentils (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018). Fats, or lipids, are necessary for storing energy, protecting organs, and aiding in the absorption of fat-soluble vitamins. Healthy fats, found in avocados, nuts, seeds, and oily fish, are beneficial for heart health, while excessive intake of saturated and trans fats can increase cardiovascular disease risk (Sizer and Whitney, 2017).

Micronutrients, including vitamins and minerals, are needed in smaller amounts but are vital for numerous physiological functions. Vitamins such as A, C, D, E, and K play roles in vision, immune function, bone health, and blood clotting. Minerals like calcium, potassium, and iron are

crucial for bone strength, muscle function, and oxygen transport (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018;Sizer and Whitney, 2017). A diverse diet rich in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and lean proteins ensures adequate intake of these essential nutrients, supporting overall health (Gropper and Smith, 2016).

Hydration is another critical aspect of nutrition. Water is essential for digestion, nutrient absorption, temperature regulation, and waste elimination. Adequate daily water intake supports physical and cognitive performance, preventing dehydration and related health issues (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018).

Dietary patterns significantly influence health outcomes. Diets high in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, lean proteins, and healthy fats are associated with reduced risks of chronic diseases, including heart disease, diabetes, and certain cancers. Conversely, diets high in processed foods, sugary beverages, and unhealthy fats are linked to increased risks of these conditions (German *et al.*, 2022). Public health initiatives and nutritional education aim to promote healthy eating habits, encouraging individuals to make informed food choices and adopt balanced diets for improved health outcomes (Sizer and Whitney, 2017).

Advancements in nutritional science have led to a deeper understanding of the relationship between diet and health. Researchers are now exploring the molecular mechanisms through which nutrients impact bodily functions and disease processes. This research informs dietary guidelines and recommendations, aiming to optimize health and prevent diseases through evidence-based nutritional practices (Capozzi and Bordonni, 2012). Comprehensive food composition databases and nutritional studies are essential tools for dietitians, healthcare

providers, and policymakers to assess nutrient intake, plan balanced diets, and develop effective public health strategies (Gropper and Smith, 2016).

In conclusion, food and nutrition are critical to human health, providing essential nutrients that support bodily functions and prevent diseases. A balanced diet rich in macronutrients and micronutrients, along with proper hydration, promotes overall well-being. Ongoing research in nutritional science continues to enhance our understanding of the complex relationship between diet and health, guiding public health policies and individual dietary choices for better health outcomes.

The field of food and nutrition is continually evolving with ongoing research and advancements. This research enhances our understanding of how different foods and nutrients impact health and informs the development of dietary guidelines and recommendations aimed at optimizing health and preventing disease (Sizer and Whitney, 2017). Comprehensive food composition databases and nutritional research are essential tools for dietitians, healthcare providers, and policymakers to assess nutrient intake, plan balanced diets, and develop effective public health strategies (Gropper and Smith, 2016).

2.1.1 Food Composition

Food is mainly composed of water, lipids, proteins, and carbohydrates. Minerals (e.g., salts) and organic substances (e.g., vitamins) can also be found in food. Plants, algae, and some microorganisms use photosynthesis to make some of their own nutrients (Rahman and McCarthy, 2021). Water is found in many foods and has been defined as a food by itself. Water and fiber have low energy densities, or calories, while fat is the most energy-dense component (Zoroddu *et al.*, 2019).

The seven major classes of food are carbohydrates, fats, fiber, minerals, proteins, vitamins, and water. Nutrients can be grouped as either macronutrients or micronutrients (needed in small quantities). Carbohydrates, fats, and proteins are macronutrients, and provide energy. Water and fiber are macronutrients, but do not provide energy. The micronutrients are minerals and vitamins (World Health Organization and Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, 2018)

The macronutrients (excluding fiber and water) provide structural material (amino acids from which proteins are built, and lipids from which cell membranes and some signaling molecules are built), and energy. Some of the structural material can also be used to generate energy internally, and in either case it is measured in Joules or kilocalories (often called "Calories" and written with a capital 'C' to distinguish them from little 'c' calories). Carbohydrates and proteins provide 17 kJ approximately (4 kcal) of energy per gram, while fats provide 37 kJ (9 kcal) per gram, though the net energy from either depends on such factors as absorption and digestive effort, which vary substantially from instance to instance (Berg *et al.*, 2020).

Vitamins, minerals, fiber, and water do not provide energy, but are required for other reasons. A third class of dietary material, fiber (i.e., non-digestible material such as cellulose), seems also to be required, for both mechanical and biochemical reasons, though the exact reasons remain unclear. For all age groups, males on average need to consume higher amounts of macronutrients than females. In general, intakes increase with age until the second or third decade of life (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

Some nutrients can be stored – the fat-soluble vitamins – while others are required more or less continuously. Poor health can be caused by a lack of required nutrients, or for some vitamins and

minerals, too much of a required nutrient. Essential nutrients cannot be synthesized by the body, and must be obtained from food (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

Fats are triglycerides, made of assorted fatty acid monomers bound to a glycerol backbone. Some fatty acids, but not all, are essential in the diet: they cannot be synthesized in the body. Protein molecules contain nitrogen atoms in addition to carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen. The fundamental components of protein are nitrogen-containing amino acids, some of which are essential in the sense that humans cannot make them internally. Some of the amino acids are convertible (with the expenditure of energy) to glucose and can be used for energy production just as ordinary glucose, in a process known as gluconeogenesis. By breaking down existing protein, some glucose can be produced internally; the remaining amino acids are discarded, primarily as urea in urine. This occurs naturally when atrophy takes place, or during periods of starvation (Nelson and Cox, 2017)

1. Carbohydrates: Carbohydrates are essential macronutrients that serve as the body's primary energy source (Gropper and Smith, 2016). They are classified into simple carbohydrates, such as sugars found in Cassava, Yam, Rice, Beans (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018). Upon digestion, carbohydrates are broken down into glucose, which is crucial for brain function and energy production in cells (Sizer and Whitney, 2017). Dietary fiber, a type of carbohydrate, is vital for digestive health, helping to maintain bowel regularity and control blood sugar levels (German *et al.*, 2022). Including a variety of carbohydrate-rich foods in the diet ensures adequate energy supply and nutrient intake, supporting overall health and well-being (Gropper and Smith, 2016). Proper carbohydrate consumption is linked to reduced risk of chronic diseases, highlighting their importance in a balanced diet (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018).

2. Protein: Proteins are essential macronutrients that play a crucial role in the body's structure and function (Gropper and Smith, 2016). They are composed of amino acids, which are the building blocks necessary for the growth, repair, and maintenance of tissues (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018). Proteins are involved in various bodily processes, including enzyme catalysis, hormone regulation, and immune response (Sizer and Whitney, 2017). Sources of high-quality protein include animal products such as meat, fish, dairy, and eggs, as well as plant-based foods like beans, lentils, and soy products (Gropper and Smith, 2016). Adequate protein intake is essential for maintaining muscle mass, supporting metabolic functions, and promoting overall health (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018). Research indicates that protein requirements vary based on age, activity level, and overall health, underscoring the importance of personalized nutrition (Sizer and Whitney, 2017).

3. Fat/Lipids: Fats, also known as lipids, are a group of organic molecules that are insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents such as ether and chloroform (Malik *et al.*, 2020). They are composed of carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen atoms, and are characterized by their hydrophobic nature due to the presence of long hydrocarbon chains (Xie *et al.*, 2018). Fats serve as a concentrated source of energy in the body, providing more than twice the amount of energy per gram compared to carbohydrates and proteins (Thow *et al.*, 2018).

4. Vitamins: Vitamins are organic compounds that are essential for normal physiological function in the human body (Thow *et al.*, 2018). They are micronutrients that are required in small amounts for various biochemical processes, including growth, metabolism, and overall health (Mozaffarian *et al.*, 2021). Vitamins are classified into two categories: fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, and K) and water-soluble vitamins (B-complex vitamins and vitamin C). Each vitamin has specific chemical structures and functions within the body (Akinleye *et al.*, 2017)

5. Minerals: Minerals are inorganic elements that are essential for various physiological functions in the human body (Hawkes *et al.*, 2015). These elements are required in relatively small amounts, but they play crucial roles in maintaining overall health and well-being (Malik *et al.*, 2020). Some of the essential minerals include calcium, potassium, magnesium, iron, zinc, and selenium, among others (German *et al.*, 2021). These minerals are distinct from organic compounds such as vitamins, proteins, and carbohydrates, but they are equally important for the proper functioning of the human body (Burton *et al.*, 2019).

6. Water: Water is an essential nutrient critical for human survival and overall health (Gropper and Smith, 2016). It constitutes about 60% of the adult human body and is involved in various physiological functions, including temperature regulation, waste elimination, and nutrient transport (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018). Adequate hydration is vital for maintaining cellular homeostasis and metabolic processes (Sizer and Whitney, 2017). Water acts as a solvent for biochemical reactions, facilitates digestion and absorption of nutrients, and lubricates joints (Gropper and Smith, 2016). Dehydration can lead to serious health issues such as kidney stones, urinary tract infections, and impaired cognitive and physical performance (Whitney and Rolfes, 2018). Daily water needs vary based on factors such as age, sex, activity level, and environmental conditions, emphasizing the importance of regular water intake to support bodily functions and prevent dehydration (Sizer and Whitney, 2017)

2.1.1.2 Food Composition Data

Food composition data provides essential information on the nutritional content of various foods, including macronutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, and fats, as well as micronutrients such as vitamins and minerals (FAO, 2019). This data is critical for nutritionists, dietitians, and food scientists as it helps them understand the nutrient profile of foods and develop dietary guidelines

and recommendations (USDA, 2020). Food composition tables and databases compile this information and are used worldwide for various applications in health and nutrition (Greenfield and Southgate, 2003).

The accuracy and comprehensiveness of food composition data are vital for assessing dietary intake and planning balanced diets (FAO, 2019). For instance, they are used to calculate nutrient intake in population studies, which can inform public health policies and nutrition programs (EFSA, 2011). These data are also crucial in clinical settings for managing dietary interventions and therapeutic diets for individuals with specific health conditions (Gibney *et al.*, 2009).

In the food industry, food composition data is used for product development, labeling, and quality control (FAO, 2019). Accurate labeling of nutritional content helps consumers make informed dietary choices and comply with regulatory requirements (EFSA, 2011). Additionally, food manufacturers use this data to reformulate products to enhance their nutritional value and meet consumer demand for healthier food options (Gibney *et al.*, 2009).

Table 1: List of commonly consumed foods in North Central, Nigeria

	Common Name	Botanical
Starchy (Roots/Tubers)	Yam	<i>Dioscorea</i> spp
	Cassava	<i>Manihot</i> spp
	Cocoyam	<i>Collocasia</i> and <i>Xanthosoma</i> spp
	Irish Potato	<i>Ipomea batata</i>
Cereals	Corn	<i>Zea mays</i>
	Rice	<i>Oryza</i> spp
	Wheat	<i>Triticum vulgare</i>
Legumes/Pulses	Bambara	<i>Vigna subterranean</i>
	Cowpea	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>
Oil Seeds/Nuts	Groundnuts	<i>Arachis hypoea</i>
	Soybeans	<i>Glycine max</i>
	Locust bean	<i>Partia biglobosa</i>
	Castor Oil	<i>Ricinus communis</i>

(Morrison *et al.*, 2016)

2.2 Non communicable diseases

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are a significant global health issue, leading to substantial morbidity and mortality. NCDs are not caused by infectious agents and cannot be spread between individuals. They are generally chronic conditions that progress slowly, such as

cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases, and diabetes (World Health Organization, 2020). According to the World Health Organization, NCDs are responsible for 71% of all deaths globally, with low- and middle-income countries bearing a disproportionate burden (World Health Organization, 2020).

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), including heart attacks and strokes, are the leading cause of NCD deaths, accounting for nearly 17.9 million deaths annually (Roth *et al.*, 2020). The primary risk factors for CVDs include hypertension, high cholesterol, obesity, physical inactivity, and unhealthy diets (Benjamin *et al.*, 2019). Lifestyle modifications and preventive measures are essential to reduce the burden of CVDs.

Cancers are another significant category of NCDs, causing approximately 9.6 million deaths each year (Bray *et al.*, 2018). Risk factors for cancer include tobacco use, alcohol consumption, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, and environmental pollutants (Wild *et al.*, 2020). Early detection and treatment are critical for improving cancer outcomes, and public health initiatives focusing on lifestyle changes can help mitigate risk.

Chronic respiratory diseases, such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma, also contribute significantly to NCD mortality (Soriano *et al.*, 2017). These conditions are often exacerbated by exposure to tobacco smoke, air pollution, occupational chemicals, and dust (Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease, 2020).

Diabetes, particularly type 2 diabetes, is another major NCD, with rising prevalence worldwide due to increasing rates of obesity and sedentary lifestyles (Cho *et al.*, 2018). Effective management of diabetes involves lifestyle changes, medication, and regular monitoring of blood glucose levels.

Addressing the global burden of NCDs requires a multifaceted approach, including public health policies, preventive healthcare, and individual lifestyle changes. Comprehensive strategies that target the reduction of common risk factors can significantly decrease the incidence and impact of NCDs (Beaglehole *et al.*, 2011).

2.2.1 Key Risk Factors of Non-communicable Diseases

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are primarily driven by a set of common risk factors, which significantly contribute to their global prevalence. Understanding these risk factors is crucial for the prevention and management of NCDs.

1. One of the primary risk factors for NCDs is tobacco use. Smoking is strongly associated with a range of NCDs, including cardiovascular diseases, cancers, and chronic respiratory diseases. Research indicates that tobacco use is responsible for approximately 8 million deaths annually (Jha and Peto, 2014). The harmful effects of smoking extend beyond the individual, affecting those exposed to second-hand smoke as well (World Health Organization, 2019).

2. Another significant risk factor is an unhealthy diet, particularly diets high in saturated fats, trans fats, sugar, and salt. Such dietary patterns are linked to obesity, hypertension, high cholesterol, and an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases and diabetes (Mozaffarian *et al.*, 2016). The consumption of processed foods and sugary beverages has been identified as a major contributor to the global obesity epidemic (Popkin *et al.*, 2020).

3. Physical inactivity is also a key risk factor for NCDs. Sedentary lifestyles are associated with higher risks of cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and certain cancers. Regular physical activity is known to reduce the risk of these diseases by improving cardiovascular health, aiding weight management, and enhancing insulin sensitivity (Lee *et al.*, 2012).

4. Alcohol consumption is another significant risk factor, particularly when consumed in excess. Excessive alcohol intake is linked to a higher risk of liver disease, certain cancers, and cardiovascular diseases (Rehm *et al.*, 2010). The harmful use of alcohol is responsible for approximately 3 million deaths each year (World Health Organization, 2018).

5. Environmental factors such as air pollution play a crucial role in the development of NCDs. Exposure to pollutants, including particulate matter and toxic chemicals, is associated with respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, as well as cancers (Cohen *et al.*, 2017).

Addressing these risk factors through public health interventions, policy changes, and individual lifestyle modifications is essential for reducing the global burden of NCDs (Beaglehole *et al.*, 2011).

2.2.2 Common Non-Communicable Diseases

1. Diabetes Mellitus

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease that occurs when the body cannot effectively regulate blood glucose levels. This condition stems from either inadequate insulin production or improper utilization of insulin, leading to hyperglycemia. Diabetes mellitus is a significant public health concern worldwide, given its increasing prevalence and associated complications (World Health Organization, 2023).

Types of Diabetes Mellitus

i. Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM)

Type 1 diabetes is an autoimmune condition where the immune system attacks the insulin-producing beta cells in the pancreas. This destruction leads to an absolute insulin deficiency. It is

most commonly diagnosed in children and young adults but can manifest at any age. Patients with T1DM require lifelong insulin therapy to maintain blood glucose levels within a normal range (Atkinson, 2012).

ii. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM)

Type 2 diabetes is characterized by insulin resistance, where the body's cells do not respond properly to insulin, and a relative insulin deficiency. This type is the most common, accounting for approximately 90-95% of all diabetes cases. T2DM is strongly linked to obesity, physical inactivity, and genetic factors. Management typically includes lifestyle modifications, oral medications, and sometimes insulin therapy (DeFronzo, 2009).

iii. Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM)

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) is a condition characterized by glucose intolerance that first appears during pregnancy. It typically resolves after childbirth but poses significant health risks for both the mother and the baby. Women with GDM have an increased risk of developing Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) later in life, and their children are at a higher risk for obesity and glucose intolerance during childhood and adulthood (Ferrara, 2007).

Causes of Diabetes Mellitus

Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM)

The primary cause of T1DM is an autoimmune reaction where the body's immune system mistakenly attacks and destroys insulin-producing beta cells in the pancreas. This autoimmune process results in an absolute deficiency of insulin, which is essential for glucose regulation. The exact triggers of this autoimmune response remain unclear, but several factors are implicated:

- **Genetic Susceptibility:** Certain genetic markers, particularly within the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) region, are associated with an increased risk of T1DM. These genetic factors contribute to the immune system's misidentification of beta cells as foreign (Gale, 2001).
- **Environmental Triggers:** Viral infections, such as enteroviruses, have been linked to the onset of T1DM in genetically predisposed individuals. Other environmental factors, including diet and exposure to certain toxins, may also play a role in triggering the autoimmune process (Knip and Simell, 2012).

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM)

T2DM is primarily caused by a combination of insulin resistance and beta-cell dysfunction.

Several key factors contribute to the development of T2DM:

- **Genetic Factors:** Family history and genetic predisposition significantly influence the risk of developing T2DM. Multiple genes are involved in glucose regulation, insulin action, and beta-cell function (Lyssenko and Laakso, 2013).
- **Obesity and Physical Inactivity:** Obesity, particularly central obesity, is a major risk factor for T2DM. Excess adipose tissue, especially around the abdomen, contributes to insulin resistance. Physical inactivity further exacerbates this condition, as regular exercise enhances insulin sensitivity (Kahn *et al.*, 2006).
- **Diet and Nutrition:** Diets high in refined sugars, unhealthy fats, and low in fiber can increase the risk of T2DM. Poor dietary habits contribute to obesity and metabolic syndrome, which are precursors to diabetes (Hu *et al.*, 2001).

- **Age and Ethnicity:** The risk of T2DM increases with age, and certain ethnic groups, including African Americans, Hispanic/Latino Americans, Native Americans, and Asian Americans, have a higher predisposition to the disease (CDC, 2021).

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM)

GDM is a form of diabetes that develops during pregnancy and typically resolves after childbirth. It shares common risk factors with T2DM, including obesity, family history of diabetes, and advanced maternal age. Hormonal changes during pregnancy can induce insulin resistance, and if the pancreas cannot compensate with increased insulin production, GDM occurs (Ferrara, 2007).

Figure 2.1: Pathophysiology of Diabetes Mellitus

Type 1 diabetes is characterized by the destruction of pancreatic β -cells by the immune system. These β -cells are essential for producing insulin, a hormone that allows cells to utilize glucose. The destruction of these cells leads to a significant reduction in insulin production, causing an absolute insulin deficiency. Without sufficient insulin, glucose cannot be effectively utilized by the body's cells, resulting in high blood glucose levels (American Diabetes Association, 2021).

Type 2 diabetes initially presents with sufficient insulin secretion. However, the body's cells become resistant to the action of insulin, meaning they do not respond properly to it. Over time, the pancreas may also start to produce less insulin, compounding the problem of insulin resistance and further increasing blood glucose levels.

In the absence of insulin, which normally inhibits lipolysis (the breakdown of fat), there is an increased breakdown of fat into free fatty acids. Without insulin, there is also an increased breakdown of muscle proteins into amino acids, contributing to muscle wasting and increased blood amino acid levels (Atkinson and Eisenbarth, 2001).

The liver responds to the lack of insulin by increasing the production of glucose from amino acids and free fatty acids through a process called gluconeogenesis. This further exacerbates hyperglycemia. Additionally, the breakdown of fats leads to the production of ketone bodies, which can accumulate and cause a dangerous condition known as diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA). DKA is marked by high blood glucose and ketone levels, leading to acidification of the blood. High blood glucose levels result in increased urine production as the kidneys attempt to excrete the excess glucose. This leads to polyuria (frequent urination). The presence of ketones and glucose in the urine, known as ketonuria and glycosuria, indicates the body's inability to properly utilize glucose and fat (DeFronzo *et al.*, 2015).

Increased urine production leads to dehydration and volume depletion, which can be life-threatening if not managed properly, Severe diabetic ketoacidosis and dehydration can result in a diabetic coma, a medical emergency that requires immediate treatment to prevent death (Samuel and Shulman 2012).

Management and Treatment of Diabetes mellitus

The management and treatment of diabetes mellitus are multifaceted, aiming to control blood glucose levels, prevent complications, and improve the quality of life for patients. Effective management requires a combination of lifestyle modifications, pharmacotherapy, regular monitoring, and comprehensive care for associated health issues.

For type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM), insulin therapy is indispensable due to the absolute deficiency of insulin. Treatment typically involves multiple daily injections (MDI) or continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII) via an insulin pump (American Diabetes Association, 2022). Advances in insulin formulations, such as rapid-acting and long-acting insulins, allow for more precise control of blood glucose levels. Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) systems are increasingly used to provide real-time glucose readings and trends, helping patients and healthcare providers make informed decisions about insulin dosing (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) management often begins with lifestyle modifications. Dietary changes aimed at reducing calorie intake and improving nutritional quality, along with increased physical activity, are fundamental (Davies *et al.*, 2018). Weight management plays a critical role, as obesity is a significant risk factor for T2DM. When lifestyle modifications are insufficient to

achieve glycemic control, oral antidiabetic medications are typically introduced. Metformin is usually the first-line treatment due to its efficacy, safety profile, and cost-effectiveness (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

As Type 2 diabetes mellitus progresses, additional medications may be required. These include sulfonylureas, DPP-4 inhibitors, GLP-1 receptor agonists, and SGLT2 inhibitors, each working through different mechanisms to lower blood glucose levels. GLP-1 receptor agonists and SGLT2 inhibitors have the added benefit of promoting weight loss and reducing cardiovascular risk, making them particularly valuable in managing patients with comorbid conditions (American Diabetes Association, 2022). In some cases, insulin therapy becomes necessary when oral medications and non-insulin injectables fail to maintain adequate glycemic control (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) management focuses on maintaining blood glucose levels within target ranges to minimize risks for both mother and child. Initial treatment usually involves dietary modifications and increased physical activity. If these measures are inadequate, insulin therapy is the preferred treatment as it does not cross the placenta and thus poses no risk to the fetus (American Diabetes Association, 2020).

Monitoring and managing complications is a critical aspect of diabetes care. Regular screening for diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy is essential. Cardiovascular disease is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in diabetes patients, necessitating the management of hypertension, dyslipidemia, and other cardiovascular risk factors. Comprehensive diabetes care also includes smoking cessation support, vaccination, and psychosocial care (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

Emerging technologies and therapies are continually enhancing diabetes management. Innovations such as artificial pancreas systems, which combine insulin pumps with CGMs, offer the potential for even more precise glucose control. Research into beta-cell replacement therapies and immunomodulation provides hope for future treatments that could alter the disease course, particularly for Type 2 diabetes mellitus (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

2. Hypoglycemia

Hypoglycemia, commonly referred to as low blood sugar, is a condition characterized by an abnormally low level of glucose in the blood, typically below 70 mg/dL (3.9 mmol/L). It is a significant concern primarily for individuals with diabetes, particularly those on insulin or other glucose-lowering medications. Hypoglycemia can occur due to various factors such as excessive insulin administration, inadequate food intake, unplanned physical activity, or a combination of these elements (Cryer, 2017).

Causes of Hypoglycemia

i. Excessive Insulin Administration: One of the most common causes of hypoglycemia in people with diabetes is the excessive administration of insulin. This can occur due to errors in dosing, misunderstandings about insulin requirements, or inappropriate adjustments in insulin therapy (Cryer, 2017).

ii. Oral Antidiabetic Medications: Medications such as sulfonylureas and meglitinides, which stimulate insulin secretion from the pancreas, can also cause hypoglycemia. These medications increase the risk of low blood sugar, especially if meals are missed or delayed (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

iii. Inadequate Food Intake: Skipping meals, eating less than usual, or delaying meal times can lead to hypoglycemia. This is particularly problematic for individuals taking insulin or other glucose-lowering medications that require consistent carbohydrate intake to maintain blood glucose levels (Frier, 2014).

iv. Increased Physical Activity: Unplanned or strenuous physical activity can lead to hypoglycemia, especially if the individual has not adjusted their food intake or insulin dosage accordingly. Physical activity increases glucose uptake by muscles, which can lower blood sugar levels (Cryer, 2017).

v. Alcohol Consumption: Alcohol can interfere with the liver's ability to release glucose into the bloodstream, leading to hypoglycemia. This is especially dangerous when alcohol is consumed on an empty stomach or in large quantities (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

vi. Insulinomas: In non-diabetic individuals, hypoglycemia can be caused by insulinomas, which are rare tumors of the pancreas that produce excessive amounts of insulin, leading to low blood glucose levels (Frier, 2014).

vii. Hormonal Deficiencies: Conditions such as adrenal insufficiency and severe hypothyroidism can also lead to hypoglycemia. These hormonal imbalances affect glucose metabolism and the body's ability to maintain normal blood sugar levels (Cryer, 2017).

viii. Severe Illnesses: Critical illnesses, such as severe infections or liver disease, can disrupt glucose production and metabolism, leading to hypoglycemia. These conditions can impair the body's ability to maintain stable blood glucose levels (Frier, 2014).

Figure 2.2: Pathophysiology of Hypoglycemia

(DeFronzo, 2015).

Glucose enters the body primarily through dietary intake. Once ingested, it is transported via the bloodstream to various tissues in the body. This arterial glucose distribution ensures that cells have access to glucose for energy and metabolic processes. The pancreas plays a critical role in sensing and regulating blood glucose levels. When blood glucose levels rise, the pancreas releases insulin. Insulin promotes glucose uptake by muscle and fat cells, stimulates glycogen synthesis in the liver, and inhibits glucose production. Conversely, when blood glucose levels fall, the pancreas releases glucagon, which stimulates the breakdown of glycogen

(glycogenolysis) and the production of new glucose (gluconeogenesis) in the liver. (DeFronzo, 2015).

The liver stores glucose as glycogen and releases it into the bloodstream during glycogenolysis. It also produces new glucose from amino acids, lactate, and glycerol through gluconeogenesis. Muscle tissues utilize glucose for energy and store excess glucose as glycogen. Adipose tissue stores excess glucose in the form of triglycerides. The kidneys are responsible for filtering excess glucose from the blood and excreting it in the urine, a process known as glycosuria. This helps regulate blood glucose levels and prevent hyperglycemia (Cherrington, 1999).

The pituitary gland releases growth hormone, which indirectly affects glucose metabolism. This part of the adrenal gland releases epinephrine (adrenaline) in response to stress, stimulating glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis. The adrenal cortex releases cortisol, a stress hormone that increases blood glucose by inhibiting glucose uptake and stimulating gluconeogenesis (Wass, 2011).

Sympathetic Nervous System: This system releases norepinephrine, which enhances the effects of epinephrine on glucose metabolism.

Parasympathetic Nervous System: This system releases acetylcholine, which has a complex role in glucose regulation, balancing the effects of the sympathetic nervous system (Samuel, 2012).

Management and Treatment Hypoglycemia

For mild to moderate hypoglycemia, consuming 15-20 grams of fast-acting carbohydrates, such as glucose tablets, fruit juice, or candy, is recommended. The "15-15 rule" involves consuming

carbohydrates, waiting 15 minutes, and rechecking blood glucose levels, repeating the process if necessary (American Diabetes Association, 2022). For severe hypoglycemia, where the individual cannot self-treat, an injection of glucagon or intravenous glucose administration is necessary (Cryer, 2017).

Preventing hypoglycemia involves regular blood glucose monitoring, adjusting medication dosages, and maintaining consistent carbohydrate intake through regular meals and snacks. Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) systems can provide real-time data and alerts, helping to prevent episodes. Physical activity should be planned with proper adjustments in insulin doses and carbohydrate consumption to avoid hypoglycemia (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

3. Hyperglycemia

Hyperglycemia, defined as elevated blood glucose levels, typically above 130 mg/dL (7.2 mmol/L) fasting or 180 mg/dL (10.0 mmol/L) two hours after meals, is a condition often associated with diabetes. It occurs when the body either does not produce enough insulin or cannot effectively use the insulin it produces, leading to an accumulation of glucose in the bloodstream (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

Causes of Hyperglycemia

i. Physical Inactivity

A sedentary lifestyle reduces the body's ability to use insulin effectively, increasing insulin resistance and blood glucose levels. Regular physical activity helps improve insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism (Cryer, 2017).

ii. Illness and Stress

Physical stress from illness or injury and psychological stress can lead to hyperglycemia. Stress hormones like cortisol and adrenaline raise blood glucose levels by promoting glucose production in the liver and reducing insulin sensitivity (Cryer, 2017).

iii. Medications

Certain medications, such as corticosteroids, diuretics, and some antipsychotics, can increase blood glucose levels as a side effect. Patients on these medications need to monitor their blood glucose levels closely (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

iv. Hormonal Imbalances

Conditions like Cushing's syndrome, which involves excessive cortisol production, and hyperthyroidism can lead to elevated blood glucose levels. These hormonal disturbances affect glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity (Cryer, 2017).

v. Genetic Factors

Genetic predisposition plays a significant role in the development of diabetes and hyperglycemia. Family history of diabetes increases the risk, indicating the importance of genetic factors in glucose regulation.

Figure 2.3: Pathophysiology of Hyperglycemia

Ritz *et al.*, 2011).

Hyperglycemia, or high blood sugar, is a condition that occurs when the body either cannot produce enough insulin or cannot effectively use the insulin it produces. This leads to an accumulation of glucose in the blood, causing a range of physiological changes.

When blood glucose levels rise, the kidneys attempt to compensate by increasing glucose excretion in the urine (Ritz *et al.*, 2011). However, if glucose levels remain elevated, the kidneys become overwhelmed, and glucose begins to build up in the blood. This triggers a series of cellular responses, including the activation of protein kinase C, the formation of advanced glycosylation end-products (AGEs), and the increase of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production (Brownlee, 2005).

These changes lead to damage in multiple organ systems, including the eyes, kidneys, nerves, and blood vessels (Nathan *et al.*, 2105). In the eyes, hyperglycemia can cause the lens to swell, leading to blurred vision, and can also damage the retina, leading to blindness (Fong *et al.*, 2017). In the kidneys, hyperglycemia can cause damage to the glomeruli, leading to chronic kidney disease and eventual failure (Remuzzi *et al.*, 2017). In the nerves, hyperglycemia can cause damage to the axons and Schwann cells, leading to numbness, tingling, and pain (Pop-Busui *et al.*, 2017). If left untreated, hyperglycemia can lead to serious complications, including diabetic ketoacidosis, hyperosmolar hyperglycemic nonketotic syndrome, and death (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2015).

Management and Treatment of Hyperglycemia

The management and treatment of hyperglycemia involve a multifaceted approach that includes lifestyle modifications and pharmacological interventions.

Lifestyle modifications:

- i. **Dietary changes:** A healthy, balanced diet that is low in sugar and refined carbohydrates can help regulate blood sugar levels (American Diabetes Association, 2020).
- ii. **Physical activity:** Regular exercise, such as aerobic exercise and strength training, can improve insulin sensitivity and glucose uptake in the muscles (Colberg *et al.*, 2016).
- iii. **Weight management:** Maintaining a healthy weight can improve insulin sensitivity and reduce blood sugar levels (Jensen *et al.*, 2014).

Pharmacological interventions:

i. Metformin: A commonly used oral medication that improves insulin sensitivity and reduces glucose production in the liver (Inzucchi *et al.*, 2015).

ii Sulfonylureas: Stimulate the release of insulin from the pancreas (DeFronzo *et al.*, 2017).

iii. Insulin therapy: Used in severe cases of hyperglycemia, insulin therapy can help regulate blood sugar levels (Davies *et al.*, 2018).

Additional treatments:

i. Blood glucose monitoring: Regular monitoring of blood sugar levels can help identify high levels and prevent complications (American Diabetes Association 2020).

ii. Continuous glucose monitoring: A system that continuously monitors blood sugar levels and provides real-time feedback (Danne *et al.*, 2017).

4. Diabetic Ketoacidosis (DKA)

Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) is a life-threatening complication of diabetes mellitus characterized by a triad of hyperglycemia, metabolic acidosis, and ketosis (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2005). It occurs when the body produces high levels of ketones, which are acidic substances produced when fat is broken down instead of glucose (Westphal, 2017). This leads to a decrease in blood pH, causing acidosis (Wolfsdorf *et al.*, 2018).

DKA typically occurs in individuals with type 1 diabetes, but can also occur in those with type 2 diabetes, particularly in the presence of insulin resistance or beta-cell dysfunction (Umpierrez *et*

al., 2018). The condition is often precipitated by factors such as infection, poor medication adherence, or new-onset diabetes (Dhatariya *et al.*, 2017).

The clinical presentation of DKA includes symptoms such as polyuria, polydipsia, fatigue, nausea, vomiting, and abdominal pain (Saxon *et al.* 2017). Laboratory findings include elevated blood glucose levels, ketonemia, and metabolic acidosis (American Diabetes Association, 2020). If left untreated, DKA can lead to severe complications, including cerebral edema, cardiovascular collapse, and death (Nyenwe *et al.*, 2018). Treatment involves prompt administration of insulin, fluid replacement, and correction of electrolyte imbalances (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2019).

Causes of Diabetic Ketoacidosis

i. Missed Insulin Doses: A common cause of DKA is the omission or inadequate dosing of insulin. Patients with type 1 diabetes rely on exogenous insulin for glucose regulation. Missing doses or administering insufficient insulin can lead to acute insulin deficiency, triggering DKA (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2009).

ii. New Onset of Diabetes: In individuals who have not yet been diagnosed with diabetes, particularly type 1 diabetes, DKA can be the initial presentation. The lack of endogenous insulin production leads to severe hyperglycemia and ketosis.

iii. Infections: Infections are the most common precipitating factor for DKA. The physiological stress of an infection increases the release of counter-regulatory hormones such as cortisol, glucagon, and catecholamines. These hormones elevate blood glucose levels and increase insulin

requirements. Common infections include urinary tract infections, pneumonia, and sepsis (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2009).

iv. Physical Stress and Trauma: Physical stressors such as trauma, surgery, or myocardial infarction can trigger DKA. These conditions elevate stress hormones, increasing blood glucose levels and insulin resistance.

v. Psychological Stress: Severe emotional stress can also precipitate DKA by raising counter-regulatory hormones, which in turn increase blood glucose levels.

vi. Pancreatic Disorders: Conditions that affect the pancreas, such as pancreatitis, can impair insulin secretion, leading to DKA.

vii. Medications: Certain medications can precipitate DKA by increasing blood glucose levels or reducing insulin sensitivity. Examples include corticosteroids, thiazide diuretics, and some antipsychotic medications (Nyenwe *et al.*, 2011).

viii. Alcohol and Substance Abuse: Excessive alcohol consumption can interfere with glucose metabolism and insulin effectiveness, potentially leading to DKA. Illicit drugs, such as cocaine, can also trigger DKA through similar mechanisms (Mishra *et al.*, 2017).

ix. Eating Disorders: Individuals with diabetes who have eating disorders may engage in behaviors like insulin omission to control weight, significantly increasing the risk of DKA.

x. Pregnancy: Pregnancy increases insulin resistance due to hormonal changes, which can lead to DKA if insulin therapy is not adequately adjusted (Mishra *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 2.4: Pathophysiology of Diabetic Ketoacidosis

Health and Wellbeing, 2016.

This imbalance is characteristic of type 1 diabetes mellitus, where the pancreas fails to produce sufficient insulin. Insulin is crucial for glucose uptake by cells, while glucagon stimulates glucose release from the liver. Without adequate insulin, glucose cannot be effectively utilized by cells, leading to hyperglycemia (Blood Glucose). To compensate for the lack of glucose, the body turns to fat breakdown for energy, resulting in an overproduction of Blood Ketones.

The consequences of increased blood ketones include vomiting, as ketones are acidic and can irritate the stomach lining, leading to nausea and vomiting; acidosis, as the accumulation of ketones in the blood causes metabolic acidosis, a dangerous condition where the blood becomes excessively acidic; and cellular dysfunction, as acidosis impairs cellular function, leading to various complications.

The consequences of increased blood glucose include osmotic diuresis, as high blood glucose levels draw excess water into the kidneys, leading to increased urine production (osmotic diuresis) and dehydration; and fluid and electrolyte depletion, as excessive fluid loss through urine results in depletion of essential electrolytes like sodium, potassium, and magnesium.

Further complications can include cerebral edema, as severe dehydration and electrolyte imbalances can lead to cerebral edema, swelling of the brain, which can be life-threatening; and shock, as the combined effects of acidosis, dehydration, and electrolyte disturbances can progress to shock, a critical condition where the body's organs are not receiving enough blood flow.

Management and Treatment of Diabetic Ketoacidosis

i. Initial Assessment and Monitoring

Upon presentation, a thorough clinical assessment and laboratory evaluation are essential. Key laboratory tests include blood glucose, ketones, electrolytes, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), creatinine, arterial blood gases, and urine analysis. Continuous monitoring of vital signs, mental status, and urine output is crucial throughout treatment (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2009).

ii. Fluid Replacement

The first step in managing DKA is aggressive fluid replacement to correct dehydration, improve circulation, and reduce blood glucose levels. Initial therapy usually involves administering 0.9% sodium chloride solution (normal saline). The typical initial dose is 1-1.5 liters during the first hour, followed by 250-500 mL/hour depending on the patient's hydration status, hemodynamics, and electrolyte levels (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

iii. Insulin Therapy

Insulin administration is critical for reversing hyperglycemia and ketosis. Regular insulin is typically administered as an initial intravenous bolus of 0.1 units/kg, followed by a continuous infusion at a rate of 0.1 units/kg/hour. The goal is to reduce blood glucose levels by 50-70 mg/dL per hour. Once blood glucose levels reach approximately 200 mg/dL, the insulin infusion rate is reduced, and dextrose is added to the intravenous fluids to prevent hypoglycemia while continuing to clear ketones (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2009).

iv. Electrolyte Management

Potassium levels must be closely monitored and managed because insulin therapy can cause hypokalemia by driving potassium into cells. If the serum potassium level is below 3.3 mEq/L, insulin administration should be delayed, and potassium should be administered until levels are above 3.3 mEq/L. Bicarbonate therapy is generally not recommended unless the patient has severe acidosis (pH < 6.9), as it can lead to hypokalemia and other complications (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

v. Addressing Precipitating Factors

Identifying and treating the underlying cause of DKA is essential for preventing recurrence. Common precipitating factors include infections, missed insulin doses, and new onset of diabetes. Appropriate management of infections with antibiotics, re-education on insulin administration, and lifestyle modifications are necessary steps (Kitabchi *et al.*, 2009).

vi. Transition to Subcutaneous Insulin

Once DKA resolves (blood glucose < 200 mg/dL, bicarbonate \geq 15 mEq/L, pH > 7.3, and anion gap \leq 12 mEq/L), patients can transition from intravenous to subcutaneous insulin. Overlap of intravenous insulin and subcutaneous insulin administration is recommended to prevent rebound hyperglycemia (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

5. Diabetic Retinopathy

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a major complication of diabetes mellitus (DM), which remains a leading cause of visual loss in working-age populations. The diagnosis of Diabetic retinopathy is made by clinical manifestations of vascular abnormalities in the retina (Romero-Aroca *et al.*, 2016). Clinically, DR is divided into two stages: non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). NPDR represents the early stage of Diabetic retinopathy, wherein increased vascular permeability and capillary occlusion are two main observations in the retinal vasculature. During this stage, retinal pathologies including microaneurysms, hemorrhages and hard exudates can be detected by fundus photography although the patients may be asymptomatic (Romero-Aroca *et al.*, 2016). PDR, a more advanced stage of Diabetic retinopathy, is characterized by neovascularization. During this stage, the

patients may experience severe vision impairment when the new abnormal vessels bleed into the vitreous (vitreous hemorrhage) or when tractional retinal detachment is present (Romero-Aroca *et al.*, 2016). The most common cause of vision loss in patients with Diabetic retinopathy is diabetic macular edema (DME). DME is characterized by swelling or thickening of the macula due to sub- and intra-retinal accumulation of fluid in the macula triggered by the breakdown of the blood-retinal barrier (Romero-Aroca *et al.*, 2016).

Causes of Diabetic Retinopathy

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a complication of diabetes mellitus, caused by the damage of blood vessels in the retina (American Diabetes Association, 2020). The prolonged exposure to high blood glucose levels leads to inflammation, oxidative stress, and vascular dysfunction, ultimately causing retinal damage (Chen *et al.*, 2018).

Other causes of retinopathy include:

- i.** Hypertension: High blood pressure can cause damage to the retinal blood vessels, leading to hypertensive retinopathy (Wong *et al.*, 2019).
- ii.** Atherosclerosis: The buildup of plaque in the retinal arteries can lead to retinal ischemia and damage (Lim *et al.* 2019).
- iii.** Pregnancy: Diabetic retinopathy can worsen during pregnancy due to changes in blood sugar levels and vascular dynamics (Diabetes Care, 2019).
- iv.** Smoking: Cigarette smoking is associated with an increased risk of developing age-related macular degeneration (Age-Related Eye Disease Study Research Group, 2019).

v. Family history: Genetic predisposition can play a role in the development of retinal diseases (National Eye Institute, 2020).

.vi. Aging: Age-related macular degeneration is a leading cause of vision loss in older adults (World Health Organization, 2019).

Fig 2.5: Pathophysiology of Diabetic Retinopathy

(Shin *et al.*, 2014)

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels. Uncontrolled diabetes can lead to hyperglycemia, where blood sugar levels remain consistently high. Hyperglycemia triggers a cascade of events, including the formation of advanced glycation

end products (AGEs), oxidative stress, and inflammation. These processes damage the blood vessels in the retina, leading to vascular dysfunction. The damaged blood vessels become leaky, increasing vascular permeability. As a result, fluid leaks from the blood vessels into the macula, causing it to swell and leading to macular edema. In an attempt to compensate for the damaged blood vessels, new, abnormal blood vessels grow on the retina, a process known as neovascularization. Both macular edema and retinal neovascularization can lead to vision loss ((Shin *et al.*, 2014).

Management and Treatment of Diabetic Retinopathy

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a major complication of diabetes mellitus that can lead to significant visual impairment and blindness if not properly managed. Effective management and treatment strategies are essential to prevent progression and preserve vision.

Glycemic Control

Maintaining optimal blood glucose levels is the cornerstone of managing diabetic retinopathy. Strict glycemic control can slow the onset and progression of retinopathy:

i. Intensive Glycemic Control: Studies such as the Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT) and the UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) have demonstrated that intensive glycemic control significantly reduces the risk of developing diabetic retinopathy and slows its progression (DCCT Research Group, 1993; UKPDS Group, 1998).

ii. HbA1c Targets: The American Diabetes Association recommends an HbA1c goal of less than 7% for most patients to reduce the risk of diabetic complications, including retinopathy (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

Blood Pressure and Lipid Control

Managing hypertension and hyperlipidemia is also crucial in reducing the risk and progression of diabetic retinopathy:

i. Antihypertensive Therapy: Blood pressure control reduces the progression of diabetic retinopathy. The UKPDS demonstrated that tight blood pressure control significantly reduced the risk of retinopathy progression (UKPDS Group, 1998).

ii. Lipid-Lowering Agents: Statins and fibrates have shown beneficial effects in reducing retinal hard exudates and slowing the progression of diabetic retinopathy (Chew *et al.*, 2014).

Anti-VEGF Therapy

Intravitreal injections of anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) agents are a mainstay in the treatment of diabetic macular edema (DME) and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR):

i. Ranibizumab and Aflibercept: Anti-VEGF agents like ranibizumab and aflibercept have been shown to improve visual acuity and reduce retinal thickness in patients with DME and PDR (Brown *et al.*, 2013; Diabetic Retinopathy Clinical Research Network, 2015).

ii. Bevacizumab: Although not FDA-approved for eye conditions, bevacizumab is commonly used off-label and has shown efficacy in treating DME and PDR (Diabetic Retinopathy Clinical Research Network, 2015).

Laser Photocoagulation

Laser therapy remains an important treatment for diabetic retinopathy, particularly in cases of proliferative diabetic retinopathy:

i. Panretinal Photocoagulation (PRP): PRP is used to treat PDR by creating retinal burns that reduce retinal oxygen demand and regress neovascularization (Early Treatment Diabetic Retinopathy Study Research Group, 1991).

ii. Focal/Grid Laser: This type of laser treatment is used to manage focal areas of retinal thickening in DME (Diabetic Retinopathy Clinical Research Network, 2008).

Corticosteroids

Intravitreal corticosteroids are another option for treating DME, especially in patients who are not responsive to anti-VEGF therapy:

i. Dexamethasone Implants: Intravitreal dexamethasone implants have been shown to improve visual acuity and reduce retinal thickness in patients with DME (Campochiaro *et al.*, 2010).

ii. Triamcinolone Acetonide: This corticosteroid can be injected intravitreally to reduce inflammation and edema, though it carries a risk of increased intraocular pressure and cataract formation (Martidis *et al.*, 2002).

2.2.3 Prevention of Non-Communicable Diseases

The life course approach is an intuitive way to conceptualise NCD prevention and control. It provides a comprehensive and sustainable framework to introduce key interventions for improved health literacy and knowledge translation. Additionally, it provides an avenue for adopting a complex systems model of public health (Rutter *et al.*, 2017).

i. Preconception and Prenatal Care

The preconception period refers to a woman's health before she becomes pregnant, and the prenatal period refers to the time from conception up to the child's birth. Evidence is growing that a woman's nutritional status during these periods may influence her offspring's health and susceptibility to NCDs later in life (WHO, 2018).

WHO recommends that before and during pregnancy, promoting healthy nutrition and regular physical activity can prevent hypertension and gestational diabetes.⁷⁸ Unborn children are adversely affected by harmful exposures such as air pollution, tobacco use, and maternal consumption of alcohol (WHO, 2018).

Focused public health policies and primary healthcare services promote access to quality services during the preconception phase. Essential interventions include monitoring weight and counselling on nutrition and exercise. These are essential components of primary healthcare, and linkages to maternal health systems can facilitate early access to prenatal care.⁷ During pregnancy, health professionals should continue weight management and support physical activity, to improve the health of the mother and her child (WHO, 2023).

Pregnancy presents an opportunity for family centred health promotion. Household members should be advised to eliminate tobacco use, to reduce alcohol consumption, and to eliminate air pollution within the home.

ii. Infancy

Infancy is an extremely important stage for the prevention of NCDs later in life.¹² A WHO systematic review of the literature concludes that a person's propensity to develop NCDs and obesity may be influenced during fetal development and infancy, and these factors may in part explain the observed correlation between health inequalities and NCDs (WHO, 2018).

Exclusive breastfeeding prevents NCDs and helps ensure healthy newborn development, as outlined in a WHO systematic review. Public policy has a key role in promoting breastfeeding,⁶ including through national labour policies supporting universal paid maternity leave and requiring workplaces to provide suitable accommodation for breastfeeding mothers, such as appropriate breaks and facilities. National efforts are also needed to restrict the inappropriate marketing of products that compete with breastfeeding (WHO, 2023).

The health system should promote breastfeeding, as outlined in the baby friendly hospital initiative, as well as monitoring the child's growth and the micronutrient status of both mother and newborn and providing behaviour change support related to physical activity, diet, or substance use, where necessary (WHO, 2023).

Infancy is also a key time for providing vaccinations, including hepatitis B vaccinations to protect against liver cancer.

A crucial consideration here is the child’s environment—in the home, in day care centres, or in nursery facilities. In structuring these environments, a primary aim is to mitigate the infant’s exposure to harmful influences such as secondary tobacco smoke, air pollution, and other environmental toxins.

iii. Childhood

Children are exposed to multiple settings where new NCD related risks may be encountered. Kindergartens, schools, and preschools are perhaps the most important, partly because most children experience them and partly because they are a good setting for health promotion activities.

Physical activity and a healthy diet in childhood are prerequisites for healthy development. It is therefore important to structure children’s environments in ways that result in sufficiently high physical activity levels and low levels of consumption of energy dense, nutrient poor foods. Health promoting schools, nurseries, or kindergartens can design their environments and practices in ways that steer children towards greater fruit and vegetable consumption and increased physical activity. Additionally, it is important to provide opportunities for children to actively travel to school such as safe footpaths and cycle lanes (Davison and Lawson, 2020).

Policy makers should also consider creating national standards for the food and drinks available in schools, placing restrictions on the marketing of unhealthy foods (including social marketing), mandating smoke-free childcare facilities, or monitoring the air in schools and public recreational settings to ensure that they meet WHO indoor air quality guidelines (WHO, 2018).

Schools are also a good place to monitor risk factors for NCDs, and the data can be used to guide national prevention policies. For example, the WHO European Childhood Obesity Surveillance

Initiative measures trends in overweight and obesity among primary schoolchildren in more than 40 European countries, ensuring the availability of high quality data to inform policy and practice, and to respond to the problem of childhood overweight and obesity (WHO, 2023).

iv. Adolescence

Adolescence, defined as the transitional phase between childhood and adulthood, is a time when young people begin developing habits that will carry over into adulthood and have large implications for their NCD risk. At this age, important settings for health promotion include healthy school environments (described above), home environments, the neighbourhood on the journey to and from school, and afterschool clubs and sports clubs.

Adolescents are vulnerable to marketing of harmful substances such as alcohol and tobacco. Countries must strengthen implementation of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control and tackle emerging risks such as electronic nicotine delivery systems (Pechmann *et al.*, 2017). Mental health also becomes increasingly important during adolescence, and prevention of bullying and provision of school based counselling are vital (Patel *et al.*, 2017).

Healthy behaviours initiated in childhood, such as physical activity and healthy nutrition, should be maintained during adolescence (WHO, 2018). A priority for policy should be to develop a coordinated response to the structural and social determinants of adolescent obesity, food insecurity, poor access to healthful food, and exposure to unhealthy environments. Although it is important at all stages of life, health literacy is highly valuable in adolescence as young people begin to make their own decisions related to their health (Pechmann *et al.*, 2017). Finally, provision of HPV vaccinations to adolescent girls has been shown to be cost effective as part of a comprehensive approach to cervical cancer prevention (WHO, 2018).

To inform policy action, it is important to collect information about individual risk factor behaviours, as well as information about the implementation and effectiveness of health promotion interventions. The Health Behaviour in School Aged Children initiative is a useful guide to measuring NCD risk factors during these important years (WHO, 2023).

v. Adulthood

The workplace is an important setting for health promotion during adulthood. Interventions that have been shown to be effective include promoting healthy food options in canteens and by offering nutrition education and counselling. Workplace policies restricting alcohol and tobacco use are important for the health of all employees. Providing opportunities and incentives for physical activity (including active transport) can promote mental health, prevent and rehabilitate musculoskeletal disorders, and improve heart health (WHO, 2018).

Policies to improve health behaviours only through workplace settings will exclude groups most likely to have NCDs, such as unemployed people. To ensure that interventions do not widen inequalities further, it is important to integrate similar health promoting interventions in other accessible settings, including community centres, churches, healthcare settings, rehabilitation centres, and recreational facilities (Warburton and Bredin, 2017).

Among the many opportunities for improving NCD related surveillance during adulthood, monitoring alcohol and tobacco use is particularly important for purposes of targeting interventions, monitoring progress, and advocacy. Patterns related to tobacco and alcohol use, physical activity, and nutrition among adults should be measured alongside socioeconomic, demographic, or geographical variables. Population based surveillance can strengthen targeted cost effective approaches to NCD prevention and early intervention (Marten *et al.*, 2018).

Governments can introduce various policies to reduce NCDs in adulthood. Fiscal policies, for instance, could tax unhealthy products such as tobacco, alcohol, or sugary drinks, and fund schemes that subsidise fruit and vegetables. Policies that promote mental health, such as strengthening leadership and governance and providing comprehensive mental health and social care services, are also beneficial at a time when people may face unsatisfying careers, unemployment, financial stressors, low social engagement, divorce, or poor emotional resilience (Thow *et al.*, 2018).

Health systems can support adults by providing universal healthcare and mental health services, screening services, brief interventions targeting NCD risk factors in primary care, and access to affordable drugs for the prevention and control of NCDs (WHO, 2018).

vi. Older People

The transition from working adulthood into retirement presents unique opportunities for promoting health as people find new ways to spend their time and resources, while also facing changing identities and relationships. It is important that as people leave the workplace, they continue to have access to support from other settings, including community centres, primary healthcare programmes, assisted living facilities, hospitals, and home care services. Measures should be taken to maintain functional capacity, strength, and balance of older people and promote nutrition for older people with diet related NCDs and micronutrient deficiencies (National Institute on Aging, 2020).

Mental health must also be targeted—for example, through policies ensuring social support at a time when people often experience social isolation, bereavement, discrimination, financial stress. This support is often provided at the local level and in cooperation with volunteering activities .

Communities must provide appropriate environments for physical activity among older people such as safe neighbourhoods, infrastructure for walking and cycling, and access to recreation facilities, as well as involving older people in wider social physical activities (WHO, 2023).

Many surveillance schemes for NCDs exclude older people, and it is worth finding ways to include people older than 69, particularly in the face of ageing populations. Having access to high quality data on NCDs and their risk factors among older people could provide insights for evaluating trends, targeting health promotion interventions, and monitoring the effectiveness of policies aimed to improve the health of older people (National Institute on Aging, 2020).

Health systems can ensure promotion of physical activity and healthy nutrition in healthcare settings and residential homes and promote physical activity and nutrition by improving the quality of advice that health professionals give to older people.

A life course approach is an underused way to approach NCD prevention and control. Unlike a disease oriented approach, which focuses on interventions for a single condition, a life course approach considers the critical stages, transitions, and settings where large differences can be made in promoting or restoring health (WHO, 2018). Importantly, it takes into account the social determinants of health, gender, equity, and human rights. It has been emphasised in numerous frameworks and initiatives in the past decade, but more work is needed to give the approach more prominence. Ensuring that the life course perspective is integrated more fully into our work will help us identify appropriate settings for health promotion, design more effective interventions, and ultimately, save lives.

Taking a life course approach requires that health literacy should be provided through multisectoral work with individuals, institutions, communities, and countries. Interventions must

extend beyond the health sector and be targeted within the natural settings that people encounter through the various stages of their lives. Taking this life course approach will help us to achieve SDG 3.4 and reduce premature mortality by 30% before 2030 (WHO, 2023).

2.3 Glycemic Index and Glycemic Load

The glycemic index (GI) is a numerical system that ranks carbohydrates based on their effect on blood glucose levels. Foods are assigned a GI value from 0 to 100, with pure glucose arbitrarily given a value of 100. This ranking system helps categorize foods as low, medium, or high GI, reflecting their rate of digestion and absorption. Low-GI foods (55 or less) are digested and absorbed more slowly, resulting in a gradual rise in blood glucose levels. Medium-GI foods (56-69) have a moderate impact, while high-GI foods (70 or above) cause a rapid increase in blood glucose levels.

The concept of GI was introduced by Dr. David Jenkins and his colleagues in the early 1980s to better understand the impact of carbohydrate consumption on blood sugar control, particularly for individuals with diabetes. By choosing low-GI foods, people can achieve more stable blood glucose levels, which is crucial for managing diabetes and reducing the risk of related complications (Jenkins *et al.*, 1981).

Recent research has continued to explore the implications of the GI. Studies have highlighted significant inter-individual variability in glycemic responses to the same foods, influenced by factors such as body composition, dietary habits, and gut microbiota. This variability suggests that personalized nutrition strategies might be necessary to effectively manage blood glucose levels in individuals (Zeevi *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, there have been discussions about modifying the GI to better reflect real-life eating patterns, as foods are rarely consumed in isolation and are

often part of mixed meals that include fats, proteins, and fibers, which can alter glucose absorption and blood-sugar levels (Patterson, 2023).

Glycemic Load (GL)

While GI provides valuable information about how quickly a carbohydrate-containing food raises blood glucose levels, it does not take into account the quantity of carbohydrates consumed. To address this limitation, the concept of glycemic load (GL) was developed. GL is a measure that considers both the quality (GI) and quantity of carbohydrates in a serving of food. It is calculated by multiplying the GI of the food by the amount of carbohydrate in grams per serving and then dividing by 100 (Salmerón *et al.*, 1997).

GL offers a more comprehensive picture of a food's impact on blood sugar levels. Foods can be classified as low GL (10 or less), medium GL (11-19), or high GL (20 or more). For example, watermelon has a high GI but a low GL because it contains relatively few carbohydrates per serving. Understanding GL is particularly useful for dietary planning, as it helps individuals make informed choices about the types and amounts of carbohydrates they consume (Salmerón *et al.*, 1997).

Incorporating low-GI and low-GL foods into the diet can offer several health benefits, including improved blood sugar control, reduced risk of type 2 diabetes, and better weight management. For individuals with diabetes, low-GI and low-GL diets can help maintain stable blood glucose levels, reducing the likelihood of hyperglycemic episodes (Brand-Miller *et al.*, 2003). Additionally, such diets are associated with a lower risk of cardiovascular disease and can contribute to overall metabolic health (Barclay *et al.*, 2008).

Importance of Determining Glycemic Index and Glycemic Load

The glycemic index (GI) and glycemic load (GL) are fundamental concepts in nutrition that provide valuable insights into how different foods impact blood glucose levels. The glycemic index ranks carbohydrates on a scale from 0 to 100 based on how quickly they raise blood sugar levels after consumption. Glycemic load, on the other hand, takes into account both the quality (GI) and quantity of carbohydrates in a serving, offering a more comprehensive picture of a food's effect on blood sugar levels to (Jenkins *et al.* 1981).

Understanding the GI and GL of foods is crucial for managing and preventing diabetes and other metabolic disorders. According to (Jenkins *et al.* 1981), low-GI foods can significantly improve blood glucose control and lipid levels in individuals with diabetes, reducing the risk of complications associated with the disease. Furthermore, (Brand-Miller *et al.* 2003) suggest that low-GI diets can aid in weight management and reduce the risk of developing type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular diseases.

In addition to diabetes management, the GI and GL are important for overall health and wellness. A study by (Foster-Powell *et al.*, 2002) highlights that diets rich in low-GI foods are associated with a reduced risk of chronic diseases such as heart disease and certain cancers. These foods help maintain stable blood glucose levels, which can prevent sudden spikes and drops in energy, thereby reducing hunger and aiding in weight (Foster-Powell *et al.*, 2002).

For athletes, the GI of foods plays a vital role in optimizing performance and recovery. High-GI foods can be beneficial for quick energy recovery post-exercise, while low-GI foods are ideal for sustained energy release during endurance activities. (Burke *et al.* 1993) demonstrated that the

timing and type of carbohydrate ingestion could significantly influence muscle glycogen storage and overall athletic performance.

From a public health perspective, incorporating GI and GL information into dietary guidelines can enhance the effectiveness of nutritional interventions. This approach can help combat the rising prevalence of obesity, diabetes, and other lifestyle-related diseases. (Willett *et al.* 2002) emphasize the importance of including GI and GL data in dietary recommendations to provide more precise and effective guidelines for the prevention and management of chronic diseases (Willett *et al.* 2002).

Examples of High, Medium, and Low Glycemic Index Foods

The glycemic index (GI) ranks foods on a scale from 0 to 100 based on how they impact blood glucose levels. Foods are categorized as high, medium, or low GI, which can significantly influence dietary choices, particularly for individuals managing diabetes or other metabolic disorders.

High GI Foods (GI > 70)

High GI foods cause a rapid increase in blood glucose levels due to their quick digestion and absorption. Examples include:

- i. White Bread: White bread has a GI typically around 70-75, causing rapid spikes in blood sugar levels (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).
- ii. Potatoes: Varieties such as baked russet potatoes can have a GI as high as 85 (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).

- iii. White Rice: Jasmine rice, a commonly consumed white rice, has a GI of around 72-89 (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).

Medium GI Foods (GI 56-69)

Medium GI foods cause a moderate rise in blood glucose levels. Examples include:

- i. Brown Rice: Brown rice has a GI of around 68, lower than white rice but still in the medium range (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).
- ii. Sweet Corn: Sweet corn has a GI of about 60, making it a moderate option in terms of blood glucose impact (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).
- iii. Oatmeal: Regular or rolled oats typically have a GI of 55-60, depending on the preparation method (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).

Low GI Foods (GI < 55)

Low GI foods are digested and absorbed more slowly, leading to a gradual rise in blood glucose levels. Examples include:

- i. Lentils: With a GI of about 29, lentils are an excellent example of low-GI foods (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).
- ii. Apples: Apples have a GI of around 36, making them a good choice for sustained energy release (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).
- iii. Whole Grain Bread: Whole grain or pumpernickel bread has a GI of approximately 50, providing a slower release of glucose into the bloodstream (Atkinson *et al.*, 2008; 2010; Louie *et al.*, 2016).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

Instruments

The following instruments was used during the research.

1. Glucometer (Blood Glucose Meter)
2. Test Strips
3. Lancet
4. Cotton wool
5. Hydrogen Peroxide

3.2 Methodology

1. Study design
2. Area of study and sampling
3. Sample size
4. Sample Identification (Via Questionnaire)
5. Sample Selection
6. Sample Preparation
7. Sample Ingestion
8. Sample Collection (Blood Collection)
9. Analysis of Blood Glucose
10. Ethical Clearance
11. Statistical Analysis

3.2.1 Study Design

Cross-sectional study design was used in this study. The study took place from 14/February/ to 18/may/ 2024. Actual data collection lasted 3 months in each of the geo-political zones.

3.2.2 Area of Study and Sampling.

Fig 3.1: Map of States in North Central, Nigeria

Source: Hope Abah Emmanuel, 2020

The North Central is the one of the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria representing the majority of the country's Middle Belt. It comprises six states – Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, and Plateau - as well as Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory.

The North Central stretches across the whole width of the country, from the border with Cameroon to that with Benin. In terms of the environment, the zone is dominated by

the Guinean forest–savanna mosaic, with the western portion falling into the West Sudanian savanna ecoregion. Plateau State is also named for the Jos Plateau, which lies in the east-central portion of the zone.

The region has a population of about 20 million people, around 11% of the total population of the country. The country's capital of Abuja, which is in the Federal Capital Territory, as well as Ilorin and Jos, are the most populous cities in the North Central, as well as the sixth, seventh, and eighth most populous cities in Nigeria.

Table 3.1: Name of Senatorial District for the Survey

S/N	NAME OF SENATORIAL DISTRICT	COMPOSITION	AREA OF STUDY
BENUE			
1	BENUE NORTH EAST	KATSINA-ALA, KONSHISHA, KWANDE, LOGO, UKUM, USHONGO, VANDEIKYA	KATSINA-ALA USHONGO
2	BENUE NORTH WEST	BURUKU, GBOKO, GUMA, GWER-EAST, GWER-WEST, MARKURDI, TARKA	MARKURDI GUMA
3	BENUE SOUTH	ADO, AGATU, APA, OBI, OGBADIBO, OHIMINI, OJU, OKPOKWU, OTUKPO	OTUKPO OJU
KOGI			
4	KOGI CENTRAL	ADAVI, AJAOKUTA, OGORI/MAGONGO, OKEHI, OKENE	OKENE ADAVI
5	KOGI EAST	ANKPA, BASSA, DEKINA, IBAJI, IDAH, IGALAMELA-ODOLU, OFU, OLAMABORO, OMALA	IDAH ANKPA
6	KOGI WEST	IJUMU, KABBA, KOGI, LOKOJA, MOPAMURO, YAGBA EAST, YAGBA WEST	LOKOJA KABBA
NASSARAWA			
7	NASSARAWA NORTH	AKAWANGA, NASSARAWA EGGON, WAMBA	AKWANGA WAMBA
8	NASSARAWA WEST	NASSARAWA, KEFFI, KOKONA, KARU, TOTO	KEFFI NASSARAWA
9	NASSARAWA SOUTH	LAFIA, AWE, DOMA, KEANA, OBI	LAFIA OBI

NIGER

10	NIGER EAST	BOSSO, CHACHANGA, GURARA, PAIKORO, RAFI, SHIRORO, MUYA, SULEJA, TAFI	SULEJA TAFI
11	NIGER NORTH	AGWARA, BORGU, KONTOGORA, MARIGA, RIJAU, WUSHISHI, MASHEGU MAGAMA	KONTAGORA
12	NIGER SOUTH	AGAIE, BIDA, KATCHA, BATAGI, LAPAI, LAVUN, EDATI-IDATI, MOKWA	BIDA LAPAI

3.2.3 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

Stratified sampling technique is used during the data collection and there are numerous approaches, incorporating a number of different formulas, for calculating the sample size for categorical data.

$$n = \frac{p(100-p)z^2}{E^2}$$

n = is the required sample size

p = is the percentage occurrence of a state or condition

E = is the percentage maximum error required

z = is the value corresponding to level of confidence required

Table 1. Sample Size for $\pm 5\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ Precision Levels where Confidence Level is 95% and $P=0.5$.

Size of Population	Sample Size (n) for precision (e)	
	$\pm 5\%$	$\pm 10\%$
500	222	83
1,000	286	91
2,000	333	95
3,000	353	97
4,000	364	98
5,000	370	98
7,000	378	99
9,000	383	99
10,000	385	99
15,000	390	99
20,000	392	100
25,000	394	100
50,000	397	100
100,000	398	100
>100,000	400	100

There are two key factors to this formula (Bartlett *et al.*, 2001). First, there are considerations relating to the estimation of the levels of precision and risk that the researcher is willing to accept:

E is the margin of error (the level of precision) or the risk the researcher is willing to accept (for example, the plus or minus figure reported in newspaper poll results). In the social research a 5% margin of error is acceptable. So, for example, if in a survey on job satisfaction 40% of respondents indicated they were dissatisfied would lie between 35% and 45%. The smaller the value of E the greater the sample size required as technically speaking sample error is inversely proportional to the square root of n, however, a large sample cannot guarantee precision (Bryman and Bell, 2003).

Z concern the level of confidence that the results revealed by the survey findings are accurate. What this means is the degree to which we can be sure the characteristics of the population have been accurately estimated by the sample survey. Z is the statistical value corresponding to level of confidence required. The key idea behind this is that if a population were to be sampled repeatedly the average value of a variable or question obtained would be equal to the true population value. In management research the typical levels of confidence used are 95 percent (0.05: a Z value equal to 1.96) or 99 percent (0.01: Z=2.57). A 95 percent level of confidence implies that 95 out of 100 samples will have the true population value within the margin of error (E) specified.

The second key component of a sample size formula concerns the estimation of the variance or heterogeneity of the population (P). Management researchers are commonly concerned with determining sample size for issues involving the estimation of population percentages or proportions (Zikmund, 2002). In the formula the variance of a proportion or the percentage occurrence of how a particular question, for example, will be answered is $P(100-P)$. Where, P= the percentage of a sample having a characteristic, for example, the 40 % of the respondents who were dissatisfied with pay, and $(100-P)$ is the percentage (60%) who lack the characteristic or belief. The key issue is how to estimate the value of P before conducting the survey? Bartlett *et al.* (2001) suggest that researchers should use 50% as an estimate of P, as this will result in the maximization of variance and produce the maximum sample size (Bartlett *et al.*, 2001).

3.2.4 Sample Selection

The selected food items will be sourced from local markets and suppliers across the study states within North Central Nigeria. Food items was sourced from local markets in North Central Nigeria to ensure a diverse representation of the region's dietary habits. Specifically, samples

were collected from Gboko Main Market in Gboko Benue state, Lokoja Main Market in Kogi State, Keffi Market in Nasarawa State, and Minna Central Market in Niger State.

3.2.5 Sample Identification (Via Questionnaire)

The questionnaires was developed and used for documenting the most commonly consumed food, their ingredients and mode of preparation. This will serve as an important background information on the food composition, dietary factors and nutritional status of a population

3.2.6 Sample Preparation

BENUE STATE

Most Consumed Food

Procedure for each food

1. Roasted yam and palm oil

Ingredients

- slices of yam
- 3spoon of palm oil
- 1/2 tablespoon of grinded pepper
- a pinch of Salt

Procedure

- Cut the yam into desire size
- Place it on the charcoal stove or put it on the fire.
- Allow for some minutes, check and change it position.
- Allow for at most 15 more minutes
- Remove from the fire and scrape the back gently

- Slices into pieces and put in a plate.
- Sprinkle your red oil, salt and Pepper or pour red oil in plate, add salt and little grinded pepper.
- Serve and eat

Moderately Consumed Food

2. Daffa (Corn Porridge)

Ingredients

- 1/2 cup of Corn
- 1 full Onions
- 3 pcs of Fresh Pepper
- seasoning cubes
- 1/2 teaspoon of salt
- 1 tablespoon of Crayfish
- 1/4 of palm oil

Processing

- Sundry the corn
- Pound and sprinkle water on the corn using mortal and pistol
- Remove the chaff from the Corn and wash it.

Procedure

- Place the pot on a cooking gas, add red oil to fry for a minute.
- Add all the ingredients and water.
- Pour the corn and stir to mix.

- Allow for at most 15 minutes to cook, then drop down

Serve and eat.

Least Consumed Food

3. Pounded yam and fresh fish soup.

Ingredients

- 4 slices of Yam
- 4pcs of fresh pepper
- cubes of seasoning
- 1/4 teaspoon of salt
- 1 Fresh fish (any one of your choices)
- 1/4 cup of palm oil

Procedure of Pounded yam.

- Peel the yam and slice into desire pieces
- Wash and arrange the yam in a pot, place on a cooking gas
- Add water and allow for at most 20 minutes,
- Check if is soft and done, then drop and pound using mortal and pistol

FISH SOUP

- Processing
- cut the fish into desire pieces
- Wash with salt and warm water.

- Blend/grind the fresh pepper and onions together.

Procedure of preparing the Soup.

- Place the pot on a cooking gas.
- Add red oil to fried for a minute,
- Pour your blended ingredient and stir, then add water.
- Add magi, salt, and the fish.
- Allow for at most 5 minutes and drop.
- Serve with the pounded yam and eat.

KOGI STATE

Most Consumed Food

- **Moi-moi (Akpukpa)**

Ingredients: Beans 8 cups

, Onions, Crayfish, Palm oil 1 cup, Seasonings (Maggi) 8 cubs, Salt one spoon, Fresh pepper and Water.

Procedure

- 8 cups of whole beans were soaked in excess water for 10 minutes.
- The soaked beans were washed and dehulled.
- The dehulled seeds were ground with fresh pepper, onions, and crayfish.
- The ground paste was poured into a bowl.
- 1 cup of palm oil, seasonings, and salt to taste were added to the paste.
- The mixture was stirred thoroughly.
- The mixture was stirred thoroughly.

- The mixture was wrapped with banana leaves.
- The wrapped mixture was steamed for about 1½ hours to cook.

Moderately Consumed Food

- **Okpa:**

OKPA (Bambara Beans/ Nuts)

Ingredients of Okpa(bambara beans/Nuts)

- Okpa flour
- Palm oil
- Grounded crayfish
- Blended fresh pepper
- Seasoning
- Sliced uziza
- Water
- Salt to test

Least Consumed Food

- **Yam porridge:**

Ingredients: yam, seasoning, salt, pepper and palm oil

Procedure: the yam was peeled and cut into cubes then washed properly. The yam was placed on the fire and the remaining ingredients were added and allowed to boil for 15-20 minutes.

NASARAWA STATE

Most Consumed Food

1. Tuwon Masara with dried Okro soup

Processing: grounding

Ingredients: Garin Masara (corn flour) Dried okro, grounded crayfish, Pepper, Ginger powder, Locust bean and Palm oil.

Quantity

- Garin masara corn powder 5 milk cups
- Dried okro (grounded) 4 tablespoons
- tablespoon Grounded crayfish
- teaspoon Ghana pepper
- 1 teaspoon Ginger powder
- Locust beans 2 medium balls and 1 cooking spoon of palm oil and Cooked for 45 minutes

Procedure/Methods

Step 1

Bring water to boil. Make a paste of some of the corn powder and pour in your boiling water. Stir till consistency is a bit thick. Ensure there are no balls formed. Allow to cook for about 12 to 15 minutes stirring from time to time. Pour the remaining corn powder and stir vigorously. Cover and allow to steam for about 3 minutes.

Step 2

Wash and put mutton in a pot. Add chopped onions and seasoning to taste. Add your locust beans powder, ginger powder and Ghana pepper. Cover and allow to cook for about 20 minutes till mutton is well cooked.

Step 3

Add your oil and grounded crayfish. Stir and taste then correct seasoning. Cover and allow to boil over. Add your dried okro and whisk thoroughly to avoid lumps. Serve alongside your tuwo.

Moderately Consumed Food

2. Cassava and Kuli Kuli

Ingredients: Cassava and Palm oil

Procedure/Methods

- Peel the cassava root.
- Slice or cut it into small pieces.
- Soak them in water.
- Boil them until tender and very well cooked.
- Discard any cooking water.

Least Consumed Food

3. Jollof Rice

Ingredient: Rice, Onion, Red pepper/tatashe, Chopped tomatoes, Vegetable oil, Maggi, Salt, Curry, Thyme and Ginger.

Quantity

2 cups of rice

1 onion

1 red bell pepper / tatashe

500ml chopped tomatoes

2 scotch bonnet

100g tomato purée

100ml vegetable oil

Maggi (seasoning cube)

Salt (to taste)

1 teaspoon curry

1 teaspoon thyme

1/2 teaspoon garlic

1/4 teaspoon ginger

2 cups water or stock

Processing

Blend your tomatoes, and tatashe together. Chop your onions and keep them aside.

Procedure/Method

1. Put your rice into a bowl and soak with hot water. Allow this to soak for 10-15 minutes. Then, wash with warm water and keep aside, or parboil your rice and wash. This is important as you will get rid of excess starch in the rice.
2. Heat your oil. Put your oil in a pot and allow it to heat up.
3. Add your chopped onions and allow them to fry. Be sure not to burn the onions in the process.
4. Add and fry your blended ingredients and pure. Allow them to fry until you get rid of the sour taste (about 10-15 minutes).
5. Add your maggi, garlic, ginger, curry, thyme and salt.
6. Mix it all together. Be careful with your maggi as you do not want it too salty (2 maggi cubes for a cup of rice). Add your stock or water, and mix too. Taste to adjust to any seasoning. Pour your rice into the pot and mix together. Make sure it is covered in the tomato sauce.
7. Cook on low medium heat. Check your rice after at least 10 minutes, using a wooden spatula to dip into the rice. This helps with getting the sauce to get the bottom of the pot, so that it does not start burning when the rice is not cooked.
8. Cook until soft. Do not overcook your rice or get your rice too soggy. When rice is soft, lower the heat and allow to simmer so the water will get completely dry.
9. Serve the rice.

NIGER STATE

Most Consumed Food

1. Moringa

Ingredients

- ½ cup of kuli-kuli (groundnut cake or chips)
- Moringa leaf
- ½ spoon of salt and
- 2-3 pieces of dried chilies pepper.

Procedure

STEP 1

- If you have a Moringa tree in your backyard, you can always harvest a bunch of fresh leaves. Otherwise buy the green leaves from markets if available.
- Remove all the stems and collect the green leaves. You can discard the stems or use it to make compost.
-

STEP 2

- Wash the green leaves in clean water and transfer to a wide mouthed vessel
- Add enough water to cover the leaves and boil till the leaves become tender.
- Drain the water using a strainer and collect the boiled leaves
- In the meantime you can also prepare other ingredients required for cooking

STEP 3

- Remove dry skin from two medium sized onions
- Chop them into pieces and keep aside
- STEP 4
- Take half cup of kuli-kuli
- Pound the required amount of Kuli-kuli using mortar and pestle. Do not add any water

STEP 5

- Break 2 or 3 dried red chilies pepper
- Add chopped onions to the pepper

STEP 6

- Add the boiled Moringa leaves to the ingredients
- Sprinkle ½ spoon of salt to taste
- Add the pounded kuli-kuli and mix it well.
- Meal is ready.

Moderately Consumed Food

2. Pounded yam and Egusi soup

Egusi soup ingredients

- A cup of grounded Egusi (melon)
- 1 spoon of pepper
- 1 piece of onion
- 2 spoons of grounded crayfish

- 4 Pieces of beef
- 3 Fresh fish
- Ugwu leaf
- 2 spoons of Palm oil
- 2 Seasoning cubes
- ½ table spoon of salt
- Water (desired quantity).

Procedure

- Wash your meat and fish
- Cook well with 2 seasoning cube and a pinch of salt
- Add crayfish and palm oil.
- Mix your Egusi paste, and pour inside the pot, after 10 minutes,
- Add your sliced Ugwu leaves to it and allow to cook for 4 minutes,
- Soup is ready.

▪ **Pounded yam**

Ingredient.

- 1 tuber of Yam

Procedure

- Peel the yam and slice into desire pieces
- Wash and arrange the yam in a pot, place on a cooking gas
- Add water and allow to cook for at least 20 minutes,

- Check if is soft and done, then drop and pound using mortal and pistol

Least Consumed Food

3. Beans porridge

Ingredients

- Beans
- Water
- Palm oil
- Seasoning cubes
- Salt and pepper.

Procedure

- Parboil the beans and rinse it off,
- Cook for the second time until it is soft
- Then add seasoning cubes, salt, pepper, palm oil.
- Meal is ready.

3.2.7 Sample Ingestion

A random blood glucose test was carried out on the volunteers before consuming 50 gram of carbohydrate in the test foods respectively.

3.2.8 Sample Collection (Blood Collection)

Blood samples was collected in five replicates at the following time points: 0 minutes, 30 minutes, 1 hour, 1 hour 30 minutes, and 2 hours. The process began with the selection of a site for blood collection, commonly the fingertip. the side of the fingertip was cleaned with alcohol swab to remove any contaminants that could affect the test result, and then a sterilized lancet was

used to puncture the fingertip. The blood was dropped carefully to the designated area on a test strip. The test strip was then inserted into the glucometer.

Start Time/ Volunteer	0 min	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min

3.2.9 Analysis of Blood Glucose

Glucose oxidase is a common method with chemistries for semi-automatic biochemistry and some biochemical analyser. This method combines the use of enzyme glucose oxidase and peroxidase. (Mcmillin, 1990, 141.) Glucose is oxidized to gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) by glucose oxidase method. Oxygen will be released by formation of a peroxidase degrading enzyme (POD) from hydrogen peroxide. Oxygenate liberates 4-aminophenone (4-AAP) and the quinonimine phenol complex is reddish. Colour intensity is proportional to the amount of glucose. (Megazyme, 2018.) The principles of the method are as follows:

The method includes two steps. The first step, glucose in the sample is oxidized by the enzyme glucose oxidase to produce peroxide H₂O₂. However, glucose oxidase is highly specific to β-glucose while serum also contains both α-glucose and β-glucose with ratio 1:2 respectively, for that reason, mutarotase also is added in some chemicals to convert α-glucose to β-glucose. H₂O₂ is formed directly proportional to glucose concentration. Then peroxide H₂O₂ continues to react

with phenols and 4 amino-Antipyrines to produce quinonimine. Quinonimine has a lotus pink colour, the colour intensity is proportional to the 16 glucose concentration. Quinonimine was measured at 540 nm. Nowadays, the amount of peroxide can be measured immediately without the second stage such as blood gas machine or hand blood glucose meter. (Bostick and Hercules, 1975.) In this research, phenol and 4 amino-antipyrine are used to form oxidizing colouring agent.

However, the serum also contains other reducing agents such as uric acid, vitamin C, bilirubin, which will inhibit this reaction by competing with the colouring agent such as phenol, an effect to the result. For that reason, 4 amino -antipyrine is added to remove the disturbance by uric acid, creatinine or haemoglobin. Besides, the reaction also can be affected by catalase which decomposes H₂O₂. (Yoo and Lee, 2010.) This method is known as an effective method with fast time and low cost. However, the other side is that many of the influencing factors can affect the response and often decrease the glucose concentration in comparison to the fact. (Yoo and Lee, 2010.)

3.3 Ethical Clearance

Ethical clearance approval was obtained from the NSUK Animal Care and Use Research Ethics Committee (NSUK-ACUREC) Nasarawa State University, Keffi with the protocol number NSUK-ACUREC/BCH/24/10-07/08/2024 and approval number NSUK-ACUREC/BCH/24/10-07/08/2024.

3.3.1 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25 (statistical packages for social sciences). The food samples were gotten using frequency analysis of food gotten via questionnaires and Google forms. In blood glucose analysis, one way ANOVA was employed to compare the blood glucose levels of different groups, in a clinical study. All data were expressed as the mean \pm std and P-values < 0.05 are considered statistically significant.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

4.1 Results

The results presented in Figures 4.1 provide a detailed overview of food consumption patterns in Benue state. These figure categorize the foods into three distinct groups: the most commonly consumed (Sweet potato, sea food, garden egg soup and semo, roasted yam and palm oil), moderately consumed (Daffa, Akoto, cooked cocoyam and palm oil), and least consumed (Sweet potato, sea food, garden egg soup and semo).

Figure 4.1: Response of foods from Benue State

The results presented in Figures 4.2 provide a detailed overview of food consumption patterns in Kogi state. These figure categorize the foods into three distinct groups: the most commonly consumed ((Apapa, Theehe, Ojechu), moderately consumed (Okpa, Ukah, Abada), and least consumed (Yam porridge, Irere, Ayicha).

Figure 4.2: Response of foods from Kogi State

The results presented in Figures 4.3 provide a detailed overview of food consumption patterns in Nasarawa state. These figure categorize the foods into three distinct groups: the most commonly consumed (Tuwon masara with dry okra soup, Yam porridge, Rice and Beans jollof), moderately consumed (Boiled cassava with palm oil, Yam and oil, Beans porridge), and least consumed (Jollof rice, Semovita and ogbono soup, Massa).

Figure 4.3: Response of foods from Nasarawa State

The results presented in Figures 4.4 provide a detailed overview of food consumption patterns in Nasarawa state. These figure categorize the foods into three distinct groups: the most commonly consumed (Moringa, Danwake with sauce, Tuwon shinkafa and okro), moderately consumed (Pounded yam and egusi, Pounded yam and stew, Beans cake), and least consumed (Eba and egusi, cocoyam, Rice beans and stew).

Most Consumed

Moderately Consumed

Least Consumed

Figure 4.4: Response of foods from Niger State

Table 4.1 shows the blood glucose levels of volunteers at different time intervals (0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes) after consuming of some selected locally consumed foods such as (Roasted yam and red oil, daffa and pounded yam and fish soup) in Benue state. It provides the mean blood glucose level for each volunteer, along with the standard deviation (SD) to show the variability in their glucose response.

Table 4.1: Blood Glucose Levels of Individuals for Most Consumed, Moderately, and Least Consumed Foods in Benue State

Roasted yam and red oil

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	83	78	84	95	72	82.40 ± 8.50 ^a
Volunteer 2	87	107	109	85	56	88.80 ± 21.41 ^a
Volunteer 3	95	94	90	59	71	81.80 ± 16.02 ^a
Volunteer 4	87	106	105	80	99	95.40 ± 11.46 ^a
Volunteer 5	88	96	88	92	86	90.00 ± 4.00 ^a
Volunteer 6	77	105	80	82	77	84.20 ± 11.82 ^a
Total						87.100 ± 13.12

Dafa (Corn porridge)

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	81	110	101	79	78	89.80 ± 14.72 ^a
Volunteer 2	85	112	125	106	113	108.20 ± 14.69 ^a
Volunteer 3	83	96	105	73	99	91.200 ± 12.97 ^a
Volunteer 4	62	88	113	57	101	84.20 ± 24.29 ^a
Volunteer 5	86	115	125	93	90	101.80 ± 17.17 ^a
Total						95.04 ± 18.07

Pounded yam and fish soup

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	67	52	129	124	139	102.20 ± 39.71 ^a
Volunteer 2	78	73	102	96	83	86.40 ± 12.21 ^a
Volunteer 3	73	77	99	87	81	83.40 ± 10.14 ^a
Volunteer 4	69	93	106	88	97	90.60 ± 13.76 ^a
Volunteer 5	68	81	86	86	85	81.20 ± 7.66 ^a
Volunteer 6	76	72	73	96	85	80.40 ± 10.11 ^a
Total						87.37 ± 18.92

Results are presented as Mean ± Standard deviation. n=5, values in same column bearing different superscript are significantly different at P<0.05

Table 4.2 shows the blood glucose levels of volunteers at different time intervals (0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes) after consuming of some selected locally consumed foods such as (Moi-Moi, Okpa, Yam porridge) in Kogi state. It provides the mean blood glucose level for each volunteer, along with the standard deviation (SD) to show the variability in their glucose response.

Table 4.2: Blood Glucose Levels of Individuals for Most Consumed, Moderately, and Least Consumed Foods in Kogi State

Moi-Moi

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	77	83	89	92	91	86.40 ± 6.31 ^a
Volunteer 2	115	96	94	83	97	97.00 ± 11.51 ^{ab}
Volunteer 3	84	91	104	88	100	93.40 ± 8.35 ^{ab}
Volunteer 4	124	121	97	83	92	103.40 ± 18.17 ^b
Volunteer 5	78	97	99	85	97	91.20 ± 9.23 ^{ab}
Volunteer 6	90	66	92	80	84	82.40 ± 10.33 ^a
Total						92.30 ± 12.40
Okpa						
Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	80	86	75	79	82	80.40 ± 4.04 ^a
Volunteer 2	72	76	73	77	73	74.20 ± 2.17 ^{ab}
Volunteer 3	79	80	73	83	83	79.60 ± 4.10 ^{ab}
Volunteer 4	66	86	80	88	95	83.00 ± 10.91 ^{ab}
Volunteer 5	71	76	81	79	77	76.80 ± 3.77 ^{ab}
Volunteer 6	99	85	77	89	97	89.40 ± 8.99 ^b
Total						80.57 ± 7.67
Yam porridge						
Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	63	86	114	101	85	89.80 ± 19.15 ^{ab}
Volunteer 2	55	101	101	98	77	86.40 ± 20.22 ^{ab}
Volunteer 3	84	94	89	83	91	88.20 ± 4.66 ^{ab}
Volunteer 4	77	78	104	104	78	88.20 ± 14.43 ^{ab}
Volunteer 5	80	77	74	84	72	77.40 ± 4.77 ^{ab}
Volunteer 6	61	101	146	122	98	105.60 ± 31.50 ^a
Total						89.27 ± 18.73

Results are presented as Mean ± Standard deviation. n=5, values in same column bearing different superscript are significantly different at P<0.05

Table 4.3 shows the blood glucose levels of volunteers at different time intervals (0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes) after consuming of some selected locally consumed foods such as (Tuwo masara and dried okro soup, Cassava and kuli-kuli and Jollof rice) in Nasarawa state. It provides the mean blood glucose level for each volunteer, along with the standard deviation (SD) to show the variability in their glucose response.

Table 4.3: Blood Glucose Levels of Individuals for Most Consumed, Moderately, and Least consumed foods in Nasarawa State

Tuwo masara and dried okro soup

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	87	116	138	175	129	129.00 ± 32.13 ^b
Volunteer 2	88	75	89	97	91	88.00 ± 8.06 ^a
Volunteer 3	82	85	95	89	68	83.80 ± 10.08 ^a
Volunteer 4	69	87	79	71	93	79.80 ± 10.26 ^a
Volunteer 5	68	97	105	90	93	90.60 ± 13.83 ^a
Total						94.24 ± 24.04

Cassava and kuli-kuli

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	137	118	100	118	112	117.00 ± 13.38 ^c
Volunteer 2	74	101	93	105	111	96.80 ± 14.32 ^{ab}
Volunteer 3	75	85	102	92	74	85.60 ± 11.80 ^a
Volunteer 4	91	113	108	101	105	103.60 ± 8.29 ^{bc}
Volunteer 5	89	97	95	92	91	92.8 ± 3.19 ^{ab}
Total						99.16 ± 14.79

Jollof rice

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	75	100	131	90	71	93.40 ± 24.02 ^a
Volunteer 2	85	87	87	92	85	87.20 ± 2.86 ^a
Volunteer 3	101	71	98	85	79	86.80 ± 12.66 ^a
Volunteer 4	88	92	109	109	95	98.60 ± 9.81 ^a
Volunteer 5	84	92	84	78	83	84.20 ± 5.02 ^a
Volunteer 6	107	76	80	94	74	86.20 ± 14.01 ^a
Total						89.40 ± 13.13

Results are presented as Mean ± Standard deviation. n=5, values in same column bearing different superscript are significantly different at P<0.05

Table 4.4 shows the blood glucose levels of volunteers at different time intervals (0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes) after consuming of some selected locally consumed foods such as (Moringa, Pounded yam and egusi and) in Niger state. It provides the mean blood glucose level for each volunteer, along with the standard deviation (SD) to show the variability in their glucose response.

Table 4.4: Blood Glucose Levels of Individuals for Most Consumed, Moderately, and Least Consumed Foods in Niger State

Moringa

Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	84	78	85	87	86	84.00 ± 3.54 ^{ab}
Volunteer 2	91	91	91	100	93	93.20 ± 3.90 ^b
Volunteer 3	91	85	90	86	79	86.20 ± 4.76 ^{ab}
Volunteer 4	54	71	76	83	94	75.60 ± 14.84 ^a
Volunteer 5	88	83	76	93	88	85.60 ± 6.43 ^{ab}
Total						84.92 ± 9.22
Pounded yam and egusi						
Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	95	95	70	100	113	94.60 ± 15.60 ^a
Volunteer 2	56	66	80	116	81	79.80 ± 22.74 ^a
Volunteer 3	85	89	100	94	83	90.20 ± 6.91 ^a
Volunteer 4	116	123	120	243	89	138.20 ± 60.12 ^b
Volunteer 5	92	98	82	91	73	87.20 ± 9.78 ^a
Volunteer 6	66	90	90	101	94	88.20 ± 13.20 ^a
Total						96.37 ± 32.09
Beans Porridge						
Volunteers/Time	0 Min (mg/dl)	30 Mins (mg/dl)	60 Mins (mg/dl)	90 Mins (mg/dl)	120 Mins (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD (mg/dl)
Volunteer 1	64	46	79	85	66	68.00 ± 15.12 ^a
Volunteer 2	94	77	85	83	94	86.60 ± 7.37 ^a
Volunteer 3	74	63	85	63	78	72.60 ± 9.61 ^{ab}
Volunteer 4	74	71	76	72	83	75.20 ± 4.76 ^{abc}
Volunteer 5	55	68	75	72	76	69.20 ± 8.53 ^a
Volunteer 6	73	88	92	84	77	82.80 ± 7.80 ^{bc}
Total						75.73 ± 11.03

Results are presented as Mean ± Standard deviation. n=5, values in same column bearing different superscript are significantly different at P<0.05

Table 4.5 Blood Glucose levels of some selected locally consumed foods in North-Central Nigeria

Foods	Mean ± Standard Deviation (mg/dl)
Roasted Yam Red Oil	87.100 ± 13.12
Daffa	95.04 ± 18.07
Pounded Yam And Fish Soup	87.37 ± 18.92
MoiMoi	92.30 ± 12.40
Okpa	80.57 ± 7.67
Yam Porridge	89.27 ± 18.73
Tuwo Masara And Dried Okro Soup	94.24 ± 24.04
Cassava And Kuli Kuli	99.16 ± 14.79
Jollof Rice	89.40 ± 13.13
Moringa	84.92 ± 9.22
Pounded Yam And Egusi Soup	96.37 ± 32.09
Beans Porridge	75.73 ± 11.03

4.2 Discussion

The result, as shown in figure 4.1 showed varying consumability of different food among the inhabitants of Benue State. It was observed that different foods were consumed by the people at different proportions shown above. Foods such as Roasted Yam and palm oil, pounded yam and ginger soup, akpu and okpa are among the most consumed foods while Daffa, akoto, cooked cocoyam and palm oil were among the moderately consumed, whereas porridge beans, garden egg and semo, ofada rice and sauce were the least consumed. It was observed that people in the study area depend mainly on locally prepared food available within the locality. This study aligns with the findings of Ene-Obong *et al.* (2013), which investigated that yam is consumed at least three times a week in north central Nigeria whereas cocoyam, daffa (corn pudding) is moderately consumed by inhabitants in north central and rice being the food consumed on daily basis by over 70% of the population in Benue State, North central Nigeria.

The result, as shown in Figure 4.2, indicate varying consumability of different foods among the inhabitants of the Kogi State. It was observed that different foods were consumed by the people in different proportions, as shown above. Foods such as Apapa, theehe, ojeuchu, are among the most consumed, while Okpa, ekwo, ukah were moderately consumed. In contrast, ijo, ayicha, irere and yam porridge were the least consumed. Additionally, it was observed that people in the study area depend mainly on locally prepared food available within the locality. This study aligns with the findings of Obayelu *et al.*, (2018), which was investigated that yam, beans, fish are frequently consumed staples in Kogi state, Nigeria.

The result, as shown in figure 4.3 showed varying consumability of different food among the inhabitants of Nasarawa state. It was observed that different foods were consumed by the people at different proportions shown above. Foods such as Tuwo masara and dried okro soup, pounded yam and egusi, yam porridge, rice and beans jollof are among the most consumed foods while yam and oil, beans porridge, eba with okro soup and akara were among the moderately consumed, whereas pounded yam with ridi soup, roasted maize, okro soup with pounded yam were the least consumed. It was observed that people in the study area depend mainly on locally prepared food available within the locality. This study is consistent with the findings of Ene-Obong *et al.* (2013), which investigated the frequent consumption of foods like corn, okra soup, and akara in Nasarawa State.

The result, as shown in figure 4.4 showed varying consumability of different food among the inhabitants of the Niger State. It was observed that different foods were consumed by the people at different proportions shown above. Foods such as moringa, dan wake with sauce, tuwon shinkafa and okro, allele (moi-moi) are among the most consumed foods while Pounded yam and egusi, pounded yam and stew, akpu and ogbono soup were among the moderately consumed, whereas beans porridge, eba and egusi, rogo and pepper sauce, cocoyam were the least consumed. It was observed that people in the study area depend mainly on locally prepared food available within the locality. A similar study by Bello *et al.* (2021) explored the food habits in Niger State, Nigeria, and found that residents primarily consume locally prepared dishes such as tuwo shinkafa, kuka soup, kunun gyada, and zobo, which are widely available within the region and form a major part of the local diet.

The results shown in Table 4.1 shows the blood glucose responses of volunteers after consuming three different meals in Benue state: Roasted Yam with Red Oil, Dafa (Corn Porridge), and Pounded Yam with Fish Soup. It was discovered that there is no significant difference in the blood glucose level of individuals after consuming the three foods in Benue State which include roasted yam and red oil, dafa (Corn porridge), and pounded yam with fish soup over a 120-Minute period. Voluteers that consumed rooasted yam and red oil are having a blood glucose level ranging from $(81.80 \pm 16.02$ to $95.40 \pm 11.46)$. This blood glucose level is within the normal postprandial blood glucose level i.e (90 to 140 mg/dL), while dafa dafa (Corn porridge) has range of $(84.20 \pm 24.29$ to $108.20 \pm 14.69)$ indicating that corn porridge may have a slightly greater impact on blood glucose levels. Pounded yam with fish soup has the range of $(80.40 \pm 10.11$ to $102.20 \pm 39.71)$. The lack of significant changes in blood glucose levels after consuming these foods may be due to the complex carbohydrate composition and the presence of dietary fiber in these traditional foods. Foods like roasted yam, dafa (corn porridge), and pounded yam are known to contain slow-digesting carbohydrates, which are broken down and absorbed gradually, leading to a slower release of glucose into the bloodstream. Additionally, the combination with fats and proteins, such as red oil or fish soup, can further slow down glucose absorption, reducing the likelihood of significant spikes in blood sugar. The moderate glucose response aligns with the findings of Egounlety *et al.* (2017), who reported that the inclusion of fats in meals could lower postprandial blood glucose peaks due to delayed gastric emptying.

The results shown in Table 4.2 shows the blood glucose responses of volunteers after consuming three different meals in Kogi state: Moi-Moi, okpa and Yam porridge, showing postprandial responses over a 120-minute period. For Moi-Moi, volunteers 2, 3, and 5 shows moderate significance, while volunteer 4 shows a significant difference suggesting a higher variability in postprandial glucose responses for these individual (97.00 ± 11.51 , 93.40 ± 8.35 , 91.20 ± 9.23). The relatively controlled glucose fluctuations indicate efficient insulin regulation and sustained energy release, consistent with findings by Ogbuagu *et al.* (2017). For Okpa, most volunteers show either non-significant or moderately significant responses, except for volunteer 6, who has a significant change of blood glucose level (89.40 ± 8.99). This is likely due to Okpa's fiber-rich nature, which slows carbohydrate digestion and stabilizes blood glucose levels. Volunteer 6 started with a low glucose level (61 mg/dL) but exhibited the highest peak at 146 mg/dL at 60 minutes, before gradually declining to 98 mg/dL at 120 minutes. This sharp spike and gradual drop reflect the high glycemic index of yam porridge, which can cause significant postprandial glucose increases, as reported by Eze *et al.* (2020). These results suggest that Moi-Moi and Okpa cause relatively stable blood glucose levels, while Yam Porridge may lead to more variability due to its carbohydrate content.

The results shown in Table 4.3 shows the blood glucose responses of volunteers after consuming three different meals in Nasarawa state: Tuwo Masara and Dried Okro Soup, Cassava and kuli-kuli and Jollof rice. It was discovered that for individuals who consumed Tuwo masara and dried okro soup, Volunteer 1 had a significantly higher mean glucose level (129.00 ± 32.13) compared to volunteers who showed a non significant difference, indicating a pronounced postprandial spike. This could suggest that this meal may cause a significant glycemic response in some individuals, the prolonged elevation may suggest a delayed insulin response. The study by

Anyika *et al.* (2019) also found that maize-based meals can significantly increase postprandial blood glucose levels due to their high carbohydrate content. For individuals who consumed cassava and kuli-kuli, volunteer 1 began with a high fasting glucose level of 137 mg/dL, which dropped to 100 mg/dL at 60 minutes, before rising again to 112 mg/dL by 120 minutes. This pattern suggests a slower glucose clearance, possibly due to the high glycemic index of cassava, which causes sustained glucose release. Similar postprandial glucose spikes have been observed in studies by Udoh *et al.* (2020), Volunteer 2 and 5 showed moderate glucose increases with mean values of (96.80 ± 14.32) and (92.8 ± 3.19) , respectively. Volunteer 3 had a lower response, averaging (85.60 ± 11.80) . Volunteer 4 had the highest mean glucose level at (103.60 ± 8.29) .

The results shown in Table 4.4 shows the blood glucose responses of volunteers after consuming three different meals in Niger state: Moringa, Pounded yam and egusi and Beans porridge. It was discovered that for individuals who consumed Moringa food, the volunteers generally exhibited moderate changes in their blood glucose levels. Volunteer 2, with a mean of (93.20 ± 3.90) had a significantly higher glucose response compared to Volunteer 4, whose mean was (75.60 ± 14.84) . Volunteers 1, 3, and 5 have intermediate glucose levels, indicating that their responses were not significantly different from either groups. Studies such as that by Kasolo *et al.* (2010) indicate that the bioactive compounds in moringa may enhance insulin sensitivity and reduce postprandial glucose spikes. The volunteers who consumed pounded yam and egusi soup variability in their glucose responses, with the total mean being (96.37 ± 32.09) . Notably, Volunteer 4 exhibited a significantly higher glucose response (138.20 ± 60.12) compared to the others, which suggests a pronounced postprandial glucose spike. This could be due to a higher glycemic index (GI) of the food combination or how it was metabolized in this individual,

reflecting differences in carbohydrate digestion or insulin secretion. The rapid glucose rise indicates a strong postprandial response to the carbohydrate-rich meal, possibly due to the fat content in egusi, which can slow glucose absorption. This finding aligns with Oboh *et al.* (2012), which showed that fat-rich meals like egusi can modulate blood glucose responses. The glucose responses after consuming Beans porridge were relatively consistent, with a total mean of (75.73 ± 11.03) , indicating more stable blood sugar levels. Volunteer 1, with a mean of (68.00 ± 15.12) , had the lowest glucose response, while Volunteer 6 (82.80 ± 7.80) , had a significantly higher response compared to some others. This suggests that while most volunteers had a low and controlled glycemic response, a few individuals still exhibited moderate increases. This suggests that the high fiber and protein content in beans helps maintain steady glucose levels, preventing sharp spikes. Similar findings were observed by Abiose *et al.* (2016), which showed that beans-based meals can significantly reduce postprandial glucose fluctuations.

In table 4.5, Foods like pounded yam, yam porridge, and tuwo masara are rich in carbohydrates. These foods cause a significant rise in blood glucose levels as they are broken down into glucose and absorbed into the bloodstream. The slight variations in the blood glucose response may be influenced by the preparation method and accompanying ingredients (e.g., soups rich in fats and proteins, such as fish or egusi soup, slow down glucose absorption). Beans porridge $(75.73 \pm 11.03 \text{ mg/dL})$ and okpa $(80.57 \pm 7.67 \text{ mg/dL})$ show lower blood glucose levels compared to other foods like cassava and yam-based meals. This is likely due to their higher fiber and protein content. Fiber slows the digestion and absorption of carbohydrates, preventing a rapid glucose spike. Protein also influences insulin secretion, further contributing to glucose regulation. Meals containing oil, such as roasted yam with red oil $(87.10 \pm 13.12 \text{ mg/dL})$, have a moderate impact on glucose levels. Fat slows gastric emptying and delays carbohydrate absorption, leading to a

more gradual rise in blood sugar. Some meals like pounded yam and egusi soup (96.37 ± 32.09 mg/dL) and tuwo masara with dried okro soup (94.24 ± 24.04 mg/dL) have larger standard deviations, indicating a wide range of blood glucose responses among individuals. This variability could be due to differences in portion sizes, individual metabolic rates, or the presence of fats and proteins in the meals that alter digestion rates. This food has one of the highest glucose responses, likely because cassava is a starchy root high in carbohydrates, and the kuli kuli (groundnut cake) adds fat, which can modulate glucose absorption, but the overall carbohydrate content drives a higher glucose level.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study revealed varying levels of food consumption across the different states in North Central Nigeria, with locally prepared meals being the predominant food choices. Foods such as roasted yam, pounded yam, tuwo masara, and moi-moi were among the most frequently consumed, while meals like porridge beans, and yam porridge were among the least consumed. The blood glucose responses to different meals varied, with starchy foods like pounded yam, yam porridge, and tuwo masara causing significant increases in blood glucose levels due to their high carbohydrate content. In contrast, foods like beans porridge and okpa, which are rich in fiber and protein, showed more stable and controlled blood glucose levels. Meals containing fats, such as roasted yam with red oil and egusi soup, demonstrated moderate glucose responses, likely due to the delayed absorption caused by fat content.

Overall, the study suggests that the type of food, its preparation method, and accompanying ingredients significantly influence postprandial blood glucose levels, with fiber and fat playing key roles in moderating glucose spikes. This information is important for managing dietary choices, particularly in the context of blood sugar regulation and diabetes prevention.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations can be made:

- i. **Promote Consumption of High-Fiber and Protein-Rich Foods:** Encourage the inclusion of fiber-rich and protein-packed foods like beans porridge and okpa in daily diets. These foods help regulate blood glucose levels, reduce postprandial spikes, and contribute to overall metabolic health.
- ii. **Moderate Intake of Starchy Foods:** While starchy foods like pounded yam, tuwo masara, and yam porridge are staple meals, their high carbohydrate content can lead to significant increases in blood glucose levels. It is recommended to limit portion sizes and combine these meals with high-fiber or protein-rich foods to slow glucose absorption.
- iii. **Incorporate Healthy Fats in Meals:** Meals that include healthy fats, such as roasted yam with red oil or egusi soup, have shown moderate blood glucose responses. The inclusion of fats can slow carbohydrate absorption, leading to more gradual glucose release. Consider adding healthy fats like palm oil, nuts, or avocado to meals to improve blood sugar regulation.
- iv. **Diversify Food Choices:** To improve overall dietary balance, encourage the consumption of a wider variety of locally available foods, including less commonly consumed meals such as garden egg, porridge beans, and yam porridge. These foods can provide essential nutrients and help in blood glucose regulation.
- v. **Educational Campaigns on Balanced Diets:** Implement community-based nutritional education programs that emphasize the importance of a balanced diet. Educating the population on how to pair starchy staples with high-fiber, protein, and fat-rich foods can

help reduce the risk of blood glucose spikes and contribute to better overall health, particularly for people at risk of diabetes.

- vi. **Monitor Blood Glucose Regularly:** Individuals, especially those at risk of diabetes, should be encouraged to monitor their blood glucose levels regularly. This will help them understand how different foods impact their blood sugar and make informed dietary choices to maintain stable glucose levels.

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